

An Exploratory Study on Sports based Scoring Evaluation Method for School Term Tests Examinations in Western Province Sports Schools

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Abstract

Sports based scoring evaluation method has been recommended by the Ministry of education. This investigation was conducted to study the functioning of sports-based scoring system for term tests in sports schools and to review the Game-based scoring system for term tests in schools, to investigate the attitudes of sports teachers and students towards the performance of sports-based scoring system for term tests in schools, to study the problems faced by sports teachers in the implementation of Game-based scoring system for term tests in schools, to study the problems and difficulties faced by the students while participating in Game-based scoring system for term tests.

The research was conducted by using three sports schools of the western province. Information was collected using 210 non-sports teachers and 18 sports teachers, 210 students from grades 8, 9, 10, 11 from one school. The data were collected by using an attitude-measuring questionnaire of sports teachers', Non-Sports teachers, and students. And some interviews were also conducted to collect the data. Data were analyzed by using percentages, table graphs and correlation, etc. Under the result There is a positive relationship between teachers' attitudes and students' attitudes towards this assessment method.

As the conclusions sports teachers have implemented the sports-based evaluation system. The students also participate in this evaluation system, earn scores and develop their skills. Transportation, human and physical resources, money, and sports supervision are the difficulties to them. Not only the involvement of sports teachers but also the involvement of schools, ministries of education, ministries of sports and institutions are necessary.

Key Words

Evaluation, , Attitudes, Problems,
Correlation, Sports, Positive, Negative

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction of the problem and background of the study.

To achieve the primary goal of education, the balance between the subject content and co-curricular activities takes a special place. Launching such strategies that can inculcate in students' qualities such as respect for discipline, adherence to rules, etc. As well as the opportunities that can contribute to the intellectual, recreational, moral and professional development of students, the launching of methods that can inculcate qualities such as leadership, discipline, respect for the law etc. in students based on inter-disciplinary activities should be done in every

school. In education, efforts are made to develop the physical, mental, emotional and social-moral forces of the individual and successfully overcome challenges, face challenges and gain self-confidence and self-esteem. Through education, it is hoped to develop many qualities in students such as coping with physical, mental and social problems, happiness and sadness, winning and losing, profit and loss and developing the ability to bear (Chandrika, 2004). It is important to have a balance between the subject content and co-curricular activities in order to achieve that expectation. It is not possible to achieve the goals of education only through academic subject knowledge, and for that, co-curricular activities should also be implemented in the school, and it is also necessary to implement and evaluate those activities. Only then will the student be motivated to participate in those activities

The national objectives given by the education reforms, especially the co-curricular activities affect the development of common skills in the students. When considering personality development as the objective of education, it can be said with emphasis that those objectives are achieved through co-curricular activities rather than teaching in class. Children who are encouraged to behave as selfish individuals in all co-curricular activities tend to cooperate with others (Hevege, 1963). Accordingly, it appears that co-curricular activities are efficient and effective in developing not only skill development, but also the development of qualities such as personality development and socialization of students.

As co-curricular activities of the school system, there are various sections like the cadet troop, youth talent, societies, etc., and the sports section is very important because it can maintain the physical and mental fitness of students and their patience. Follow the rules. As sports help to develop good character traits such as discipline and create various skills and good attitudes, school sports are a great help in the development of students as well as directing their lives in the right direction. And sociability in sports activities. Mental rejuvenation etc. characteristics are evident (Jayasuriya, 2006). According to that, it is possible to get opportunities and experiences through sports to build the attitudes, skills and mental balance necessary for living and the good training, good

knowledge, physical health and mental health caused by sports. It is clear that it helps to provide good education to the students. Accordingly, the school playground will be a good place to develop a pattern of behavior that is favorable to society. Accordingly, it seems that by directing the student to sports through the right guidance and evaluating their sports skills, suitable behaviors can be developed in the students for a good life in the future.

Patience, victory and defeat according to the new education reforms. Developing the ability to present, help each other, cooperate, lead, etc., has allowed the implementation of a consensus education system in schools in such a way that every citizen can be given the full opportunity to achieve at the maximum level. There too, an important place has been given to the sports department in schools.

Although the new education reform recognizes the importance of sports education and expects to make it an active section in schools, a formal plan must be implemented to achieve the purpose of the sports section. But a knowledge-based society has been built in schools nowadays, focusing only on the exam (Holpman, 2004). Accordingly, in this kind of background, it appears that students are trained only to face competitive exams. Actions should be taken to prevent under-proneness. Also, when going to implement sports under a formal plan, when looking at the sports facilities in schools, it has become a strong problem that physical and human resource imbalances in rural areas, especially for sports, can be seen compared to schools in urban areas.

The Kannangara report, which focuses on the sports field in relation to the implementation of sports in schools, has organized every sport in the school.

Specializing in the field of sports regarding the implementation of sports in schools indicates that it is not possible and the number of resources required for that should be sufficient. The same states that it is important that the sports chosen are suited to the various abilities of the students, and hockey for boys. Sports such as cricket, football, rugby, soccer and local sports and sports such as Netball, Elle and hockey for girls are also recommended for both swimming. Also, it is essential to motivate as many students as possible for sports without focusing on a small

group of students and by organizing sports events, it is emphasized that the school will show its strength as well as it will make the students proud of their school. Accordingly, it is clear that some recommendations have been made on how to implement sports in the school. Accordingly, if the sports department is maintained in schools only nominally, it will not be possible to reach the desired goals and in order to reach those goals, it seems necessary to maintain it in the schools under a formal plan at an active level. ED dated 19.03.2014 by the Ministry of Education to give marks to the progress report book for participation in sports. The government has decided to implement it in every school under the circular document 1/15/2/4/26. A National Sports Development Program has been prepared by a sports board formed at the national level for school sports development and these programs have been launched by making sports compulsory in every school. According to the circular dated 19.03.2014 of the Ministry of Education,

"The Ministry of Education has decided to allow every student to engage in some kind of sport just as every student is given an education. According to the Cabinet- approved school sports development program, sports have been made compulsory for school students except for disabled students. Accordingly, for the school term examination which is conducted at the end of every school term, the necessary arrangements have been made to give marks to the progress report book of every student considering sports as compulsory....

It has been decided to give 100 marks for the following 3 activities while giving marks for the progress report notebook.

1. 60 marks on participation in training for any sports or activities of under-skilled or student-butt,
2. 20 marks on active contribution to the morning fitness program,
3. 20 points are also awarded for the sports activities organized by the school per term.

Although such a system has been recommended by the Ministry, this is not formally implemented in every school and it can be seen how various problems have arisen in the implementation of the schools. So researcher hopes to diagnose what the problem is. For that purpose, it is being studied how this program works by giving marks to the

students in the schools where this evaluation system is currently in operation. In addition, the attitude of teachers and students towards this game-based assessment system is also investigated. Finally, this study hopes to further develop this game-based evaluation system in schools and develop an interest in the game among the students.

1.2 Significance of the Study

Kannangara report which focuses on every sport organized in the school. Sports and exercises outside the classroom were considered important aspects since the Kannangara. Sports, which is a necessary element for the mental development of students as well as physical development, is very helpful in maintaining the mind properly. It is important to pay attention to the extent to which the program of the school sports department is used in the work of building a good citizen who is expected to be empowered by education. This study is very important to know to what extent this game-based assessment method has been helpful in motivating students to play sports with the aim of developing sports skills in students. Also, this game-based evaluation system is helpful to free the students from the constant exam-centered mentality and adjust their physical and mental condition.

Also, how the personality of the student is built and how the multifaceted intelligence of the students is developed can be seen by studying the manner in which this game-based assessment system is implemented in the school.

Thus, although there is a program to promote sports, this evaluation system is not implemented successfully in every school in Sri Lanka and it can be seen that there are some problems in the schools that are active and in the implementation. So, this study is done based on this game. Find out if this evaluation system is being implemented properly in the school,

It can be known by studying the working nature.

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To find out if this evaluation system is being implemented properly in the school. Because if this evaluation is not done properly by using the relevant teachers, it will not be possible to achieve the purpose of social development, encouraging students to play sports, developing the personality of students, and producing a student with physical and mental strength. Therefore, there is a need for this evaluation system to be implemented in the school according to a proper plan under a proper system. Through this study, it is important to study the various attitudes of teachers and students towards this evaluation system and its form and to build a good attitude towards sports in the school student community.

And although the sport is often limited to the first term of the school only, through this evaluation system there is the possibility of participating in the sports activities of the students every year. But throughout the year, various problems have arisen for the students and sports teachers in the implementation of the sports evaluation system in different schools. Since no in-depth study has been done on this kind of problem, this study is an important study for the entire school system.

Presenting solutions and suggestions for these problems, developing the sports promotion program and developing a good attitude towards the school community to practice sports, this study is also very important because it is expected to produce a student with a serious personality.

2.Literature Review and Theoretical Frame Work

2.1 The game and its history

As one of the components of industrial education, sports are firmly established in human society. The history of sports goes back as far as human existence. "Sports" or the word sport is a French word that means entertainment. The word "desportor" is also broken.

That is, it is impossible to say exactly when and how the game was born, but its meaning is a reed made from a French word. The meaning of the word "sports" nine sports is entertainment, it is clear that sports provide exciting pleasures. That is, it is clear that sport is important to remove the oppressive conditions of the human being and create mental satisfaction.

Also, sport has been introduced as in the British Encyclopedia. Recreation Channeling physical energy into tasks or competitive tasks. Activities are introduced as games. That is, recreational activities such as running, jumping, throwing, etc., for any recreational activities that give joy or to perform those activities in a fun way, are defined as sports. This reveals that the competitiveness of the game is determined by the dynamic between each other, and as the efficiency increases, so does the entertainment. Accordingly, this sloppiness will be in the history of entertainment. It is confirmed that it developed through human activities. It is further confirmed by the following ideas.

As shown in the special report (1982), man has been involved in natural activities such as running and jumping since the beginning of time. In the age of wilderness, man was naturalized to hunt animals for food and shelter. Used to run. It is also indicated that animals used to make shawarma and jump over hurdles, climb up and down hills, ride on vines, and beat animals with weapons made for sustenance. MiHta) shows the stomach used to compete these actions even in the most developed nature.

Also, the time when man started to organize himself as an individual in the society. Especially the interaction with other people indicates that the history of the game is old until the wind phase. There are many special purposes of games, There are five main things are shown below.

1. Physically demanding sports to maintain a state of abdication
2. Enhancing the interest of the spectators and the players by displaying the skills,
3. Bigger numbers tend to be emotionally draining for binge-watchers.
4. Lack of opportunity to participate in and enjoy the games by rioting or taking steps to spoil the game,
5. Participate in festive occasions to help maintain camaraderie and stay refreshed. According to that, it is clear that the game was said to have existed before the beginning of human civilization and that the game developed naturally with the habits of human life. And also to create entertainment through oppression, twenty-speed away It is revealed that the game has existed since history based on specific objectives such as creating wisdom.

This reveals that the game has existed since history based on specific objectives such as creating friendship. A game is defined as a physical process organized under a set of rules and free behavior without coercion, as defined in Jan Huynh Gass's book "Man is a player" (Minor and Sub-Sports Module 111207, 1982) i.e. a series of free actions under a set of rules without influence from anyone. It is defined as a physical process that can be carried out according to the will of the individual. It is clear that a set of rules of the game tries to create law-abidingness, disciplinedness, fairness and equality.

Also, as the Special Report (1982) shows, sport is one part of physical education implemented in today's schools. It has a specific control organization, rules, or customs that explain the goals and limits of human behavior. has been introduced as Accordingly, as well as the ideas explained so far, this definition also reveals that sport is a variety of challenging action sports where the end result is determined by physical strength.

Physical exercise originated in Greece, and the Greek laws of sports are still in force today. The Spartans in Greece paid special attention to things like gymnastics and music in their education. The elephants have indicated that things like gymnastics should be an integral part of education (Organization of Competitions, 1991) and as Gunawardena (1988) points out, the ancient Olympics, which were limited to Greeks only, were held in Greece in 766 BC. Only one race was held at the Games. The match was called "Stadium" and marked the first victory for the Greek chorus. Long jump, discus throw, javelin throw are included in this Olympics. The Romans are credited with introducing the Olympic Games to the world, such as wrestling, weightlifting, and gymnastics. Also, 1886 marks the beginning of the modern Olympics in Athens, Greece, and marks the beginning of international sports events. Accordingly, it is revealed that the Olympic Games gave the opportunity to open the sports history to the world and the Greeks and Romans have been honored.

According to the above definitions, sports is a very broad subject area. It also indicates that sports are activities that consume physical and mental energy. That Accordingly to it, it is revealed that both types of sports that consume physical and mental energy are included in the

physical education curriculum. Accordingly, it is clear that the practical part in the school curriculum is sports.

It is also clear that sports have been intertwined with the human community since the beginning of history. It is clear that since the beginning of history, man has engaged in various sports because it is very useful for maintaining his health condition and for maintaining his lifestyle.

Thus, the history of sports extends to the early beginnings of humans and it can be seen that sports have been very useful in mastering the nature and environment of humans. Sports involve people developing and training their skills for their own well-being, and parallel training of their own usefulness is revealed. All this reveals that since the past, sports have been intertwined with human life and developed along with human evolution.

2.2 How sports have been included in the school curriculum in Sri Lanka

According to the Education Century (1969), the British government established the Department of Public Instruction in Sri Lanka in 1870 and introduced "drills" to schools to teach discipline and to make the body more subtle in movement. It is also shown that by 1891, drill and physical training courses were part of the curriculum. Accordingly, it is clear that during the colonial era, the British government started by introducing the basic background required for sports by introducing drills. Also, the law enacted in 1920 mandated two hours of physical training per week for all students. Student volunteers formed pipe bands and boys' corps. The purpose of starting these organizations at the school level was to impart training to suitable boys for army training so that they can be recruited into the army and police. That was accepted. Sports activities will have a special place in the camps organized by these organizations. The Sports Association is a direct result of the athletics held at the Student Reed Corps Camps in Sri Lanka. Accordingly, the function of physical training in schools was changed to physical education in 1947.

(Special Report, 1982, page 9) That is, according to this report, it is clear that the purpose of recruitment to security forces such as the army and the police was also given physical training and the primary purpose was to provide security to the country. Also in

sports broadcasting, the beginning of today's common course association is revealed as a result of the sports training conducted in these camps.

Competitions at varsity, staff, district and national levels were conducted under the control of the Ministry of Education and other such tournaments were conducted by voluntary varsity sports associations such as Sri Lanka varsity athletics association. (Special Report, 1982, page 10) Accordingly, it is clear that the Ministry of Education as well as the Voluntary School Associations started conducting sports matches during sports broadcasting.

According to Circular No. 45 of 1956, the curriculum of Grades 1-5 included physical and aesthetic activities as well as creative activities. A physical exercise subject called Physical Studies was included in the Junior Secondary Curriculum. Thus, it is clear that since sports are an essential element for both primary and secondary aspects, efforts have been made to include them in the school curriculum.

After coming to power in 1970, the education reform proposals presented in 1972 gave a special opportunity to physical education subjects and sports.

Allotment of 3 periods per week for the subject of Health and Physical Studies for Grades 6-9. At the end of Grade 9, Health and Physical Studies was made a compulsory subject with a practical test in the National Common Certificate Examination.

According to the facts given above, it appears that not only the inclusion of sports in the curriculum but also its development has been brought about. It is clear that allocating more periods, conducting practical tests, making it a compulsory subject, etc. have been further promoted in the school curriculum

As Dep (1969) indicates, this led to the recognition of the need for physical education and sports for every school-going child. Accordingly, it is clear that due to the necessity of the game, there was an acceptance of the game among the students and it was the reason for the motivation of the game among the students.

In 1978, the education system was changed again. Therefore, there was a change in these methods. 1 period per week for the subject of physical education and 2 periods for the

subject of health education are currently being implemented for grades 6, 7, and 8. Certain measures to coordinate the activities of the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Sports regarding the development of sports activities are implemented (Special Report, 1982, p. 10). According to that, it is clear that even though the sports were included in the curriculum in 1972 and promoted, the 1978 education system canceled the practical tests for sports, so it appears that it has affected the students away from sports.

In 2014, the Ministry of Education has informed the principals to give marks to the progress report book for sports in every semester examination under circular ED 1 15 2 /4 /26. In the scoring system for sports, more weight has been given only to participate in sports training in the evening, so students are expected to choose a sport and participate in sports training in the evening. The criteria and methodology for awarding marks have been prepared by the Ministry of Education. Also, according to the circular issued by the Ministry of Education dated 20.05.2014 ED 1/15/2/4/6, special and urgent attention has been given regarding the implementation of the school physical health program. Every principal has been instructed by circular 2006/4 and letter dated 2006.3.18 to carry out the school physical health program every day with the start of school. Accordingly, it is clear that the Ministry of Education and the Sports Promotion Committee have taken various steps to include sports in the school curriculum. This reveals that the awarding of points for playing games and the mandatory implementation of physical fitness programs have been included in the school curriculum.

According to the above information, the inclusion of sports and physical education in the school curriculum implemented by various educational reforms.

You can get a clear understanding of how. That is, because it was recognized that sports are essential for building a person with a balanced personality, it appears that these kinds of educational reforms have included sports in the school curriculum.

2.3 Importance of Sports in Personality Development

The purpose of education is the development of personality, and according to this, sports are popular as well as an extra-curricular activity

that plays an important role in shaping the personality of the student. Therefore, building a good family personality in the individual has been recognized as one of the most important educational objectives in building a working and good citizen of the country. Considering the definitions presented about personality, different psychologists have interpreted personality in different ways, but all of them can show that sports play a similar role in the development of the force that is meant as personality. As a place to improve one's personality, the American educator named Allpot has been mentioned in the book *Personality: A physical interpretation*. In giving a comprehensive definition of personality, the characteristics that must be included are the social or social structure of having a personal structure that can shape every process to suit the appropriate culture. One's personality is shaped and greatly influenced by one's behavior in sports and physical exercise.

According to Cosman (1960), in a survey of a group of students studying in a classroom, it is shown that the students who perform better in the playground have the ability to control emotions and have the ability to tolerate other students. Moreover, because they have a healthy mind and a healthy body, it indicates that they have the ability to mold their personality to be suitable for a democratic society. It has been further shown that not only every posture and physical activity of such students is shaped with balance, but they have the ability to accept every obstacle encountered in the path of life with a smile. Accordingly, according to the above idea, it is clear from this research that sports are not a help for the students who are involved in sports to build their personality physically, mentally and socially than the students who are not involved in sports

And according to Acharya Jayasuriya (1979), social isolation is still the main disadvantage of personality development. Boys need opportunities to mix with boys and girls with girls to exchange ideas, and this can be done in the transition from class to class, in the lunchroom, in the playhouse and in the assembly hall, for example. He states that participation in team sports such as basketball, netball, and soccer is particularly important for some girls and boys, and participation in team sports such as basketball, netball, and soccer is

beneficial for most boys. Personality growth and development Arabaya states that acceptance of children by teachers is also important and many students do not feel accepted in their homes. It is also stated that some children live at home as a government guardian and some feel that they will not get the love of their parents and compete with their siblings for that too. That is why he states that it is especially necessary for such students to be accepted by the course and the teachers. It is also said that due to the friendship between children and teachers in the playground, recognition is especially created in the child. And because of all these things, it is indicated that children's emotional sports safety is growing in the playground. According to this research, it is revealed that sports are a good help to eliminate social isolation and create sociability in personality development. Also, this test reveals that sports are important for building a balanced personality in the student by creating needs such as acceptance of interpersonal relationship, love care etc.

According to Kosman (1960), every thought and physical activity of the person is linked together like links in a chain. When angry, the face becomes red, when thinking too much about certain things, gastric diseases and injuries, lack of nutrition, lack of desire in life, broken hopes for the future, increased heart rate when afraid, indigestion and physical pain etc. indicates According to him, it is clear that human thoughts and physical activities are linked together and when there are changes in thoughts, the personality is affected by having to suffer physical diseases and this research shows that if you engage in physical activities based on good thoughts, you can create a balanced personality from those stressful.

As Athukorala (2003) points out, early childhood. The child who comes to the center does not study subjects and lives in the preschool. It is said that during his life, he is satisfied by doing various sports activities, singing and acting. The pre-school teacher should do the activities and games in a meaningful way to build and handle the full attention of the children and develop the necessary guidance and facilities for that. Accordingly, it is revealed that children learn life through games from a young age. And this reveals that sports are essential to learn life by engaging in sports activities from a young age

and gradually develop personality as they grow up.

According to Swarnasiri (2016), sports have many benefits for physical development and personality development. It is said that sports lead to regular existence and health of the body and there are also many sports aimed at mental development. And overall, the training gained from any sport directly contributes to mental and physical healing and also allows for physical and mental relaxation for the children who have learned the subject matter. Various sports and their disciplinary rules training, experience of winning and losing, respect for decisions, cooperation, determination and dedication, obedience and agility etc. also indicate that a set of qualities can be included in life with sports. Accordingly, through these ideas, it appears that sports are important to get rid of the exam-centered mentality and provide physical and mental rest to the student. This reveals that sports are important for the personality development of students as any sport provides physical and mental health.

Sports are very important for the development of the individual's personality internally such as healing the condition very quickly, becoming a healthy long life recipient etc. And respect for discipline. Protecting laws, successful completion of collective activities, ability to make correct decisions. Being ethical. Being truthful This reveals the necessity of standing up for the rights of others, becoming a good person and engaging in sports to become a citizen with a balanced personality that brings glory to the village and the country.

2.4 Evaluation

Evaluation methods have been used since the past to measure the amount or achievement of the student in the learning and teaching process. Although it is called by different names such as testing, measurement, assessment, examination, the task assigned to it is the same. Appraisals are a constant part of our lives, not alien.

Corroborating these ideas, Senaratne (1999) points out that we are used to making different evaluations in our normal life. The shirt is well-stitched, the designs of the saree are beautiful, and Sugathapala is good at learning are frequently heard. In the background of this statement, there is some systematic and

psychological method of data acquisition and data interpretation. In the end, statements like these come across as judgmental. Therefore, evaluation is a feature that is integrated with our life and not a foreign function of religions. According to this, it is clear that evaluation is something related to our life in the past and not something foreign and the interpretation of the obtained data has been introduced as evaluation.

According to Markelwala (2000), evaluation is defined as systematically collecting data and basing that data on an observational interpretation and making a judgment and then acting on that judgment. Also, Muthulingam (1979) defines evaluation as a process of providing information for making various judgments and decisions. Accordingly, the systematic collection of data in the evaluation, their observation and interpretation. This makes it clear that judgment is decided upon.

According to Satterley (1981) assessment means sitting next to the student and observing him when necessary and helping him. Accordingly, it is clear that monitoring and guiding students when they need help has been interpreted as evaluation.

According to the overall views expressed above, it is clear that the sport has a direct impact on the personality development of the student. It has been confirmed by the opinions presented by various educationalists and psychologists.

This makes it clear that the students who are engaged in exam-oriented education get good support through sports to develop their personality. Physical and mental well-being is essential to a student's personality and it is best provided through sports activities, increasing body muscle activity, increasing body strength, overcoming laziness and laziness, and building endurance. Activity and body flexibility, external pressure, self-confidence. Navaratne (1996) states that the student acquires knowledge only if he is properly engaged in the learning, teaching and assessment process. Accordingly, according to the above definition, obtaining information about the development of the student's social, motivational, and psychodynamic areas can also be interpreted as a principle of interpretation.

Evaluation In relation to the literature review discussed so far on definitions, the concept of evaluation is an extremely important function

associated with the learning and teaching process. With the aim of bringing about behavioral change through the cognitive, motivational and psychokinetic fields, every process in which school students participate is involved in the evaluation. The data provided for evaluation according to the information about the student's achievement level in the learning process is used to develop the quality and adequacy of the learning and teaching process. Assessment Assessments can be implemented to assess the skills and abilities of students in programs, games, innovation, etc., carried out in classrooms as well as externally. Assessment is also described as a process that helps the teacher identify the student during learning that creates opportunities for students to improve. It can be described as a method that can be used to measure the student's social and psychomotor skills by being with the student based on the various decisions and judgments made by the evaluation and providing him with feedback at the time of need, while the influence of external factors on his ability structure and performance is not less.

2.5.Measures used to develop sports in Sri Lanka

The school education process should be prepared to prepare a necessary background to endow our country with a healthy citizen with good qualities of physical and mental balance. To accomplish that task, the school sports department has a unique place. Therefore, the measures taken for the development of various school sports will be studied.

The National Education Commission (1992) report states that a balanced education should provide an understanding of moral values and values related to life. Furthermore, in this report, it is further stated that activities related to the development of special talents, exercises that improve physical health and the improvement of various physical skills should be developed in schools.

Accordingly, it appears that this report has emphasized that for a balanced education, knowledge and moral values as well as exercise and physical activities that improve body health should be developed. And the need and importance of developing sports in the school is also revealed.

Physical and mental as stated in the Annual Performance Report (2016). By the Ministry of Education to produce a fit person.

The following game development programs have been launched.

- Engage every student in some sport.
- Engaging primary school students in daily physical activity,
- Implementation of physical fitness programs for students in the secondary sector. In school exams, sports skills are evaluated and students are given marks
- To develop sports talented students to international levels
- Creation of training pools at the national level for
- Establishing the 2017 - 2020 School Sports Development Plan.
- Recruitment of 3850 new sports coaches.
- Conducting all-Island and athletics tournaments.

According to this, it is clear that the Ministry of Education has taken many measures to promote sports as it affects a serious education. It is also clear that further research is needed regarding their functionality.

2.6 Actions used to develop the game in foreign countries

As Pedly (1984) points out, physical education and organized sports in England have been given an integral place in the curriculum of every school. Primary education is for students from 5-11. During this stage, children are directed to physical education for a longer period of time. Throwing, climbing, bending, swimming, etc., are mastered by the children through the game itself. These physical exercises and games are very helpful in developing new abilities and developing innate abilities. And even at the regional level, the government spends a lot of money to provide physical facilities for sports to all the schools of the education boards. Social Providing physical education to all children between 11-18 years living in every school regardless of class differences, intelligence etc., sports such as swimming, cricket, football, hockey, tennis, netball among organized sports have been made compulsory. Thus it is clear that in England sports have an important place in the curriculum of every school. Therefore, it is clear that it has affected the promotion of the game. And by making sports compulsory

regardless of class, it is clear that sports are an essential factor for school students. Also, it appears that good measures have been taken for the development of sports activities by providing the necessary physical facilities at the local level for daily activities. All these matters reveal that many measures have been taken to promote the game in England.

The Chinese People's Government has paid special attention to sports in the education process since 1949. According to Free China Review (1983), the government has established 2 main organizations to improve the sports sector. They are

1. Physical Education and Sports Commission of the People's Republic of China
2. the All China Sports Council.

It is also said that in China, 3-4 hours a day are spent in sports and in Chinese schools, sports are given more facilities than learning. It is stated that sports and physical education have been added to the curriculum of primary, post-primary, and higher education in all areas of equal importance (women of the china, 1995). Accordingly, it is revealed that the Chinese government has set up various organizations to develop the game. And by giving more facilities to sports than learning, it is clear that since sports is an essential factor, measures have been taken to develop it further. It is also revealed by giving equal importance to sports in every aspect of education.

According to Pliem (1998), every school in America must appoint a trained sports teacher and annual sports events are held in the school and training camps are held for sports. The development of sports in these schools is expected to fulfill basic needs in the student, to practice team spirit and leadership. The democratic social pattern implies the development of qualities such as self-confidence and equality. Accordingly, the American government also developed the game

This shows that steps have been taken. This also reveals that students are directed to sports, especially with the aim of tending to a democratic social pattern. This also reveals that there are measures to develop sports by appointing training sports teachers, holding annual sports events and training camps.

According to Sumathipala (1970), In Russia a good school called Yasli is maintained for the protection of the physical development and

health of infants. Sports are compulsory in schools and the sports section is subsumed under the beauty section. It also hosts annual national festivals for sports. According to this, it is clear that the Russian government has taken various measures to develop sports by giving importance to sports and health safety and making sports an integral part.

In India, even though the government has given priority to physical education and plans to develop the school sports sector, it is not done properly in the states due to poverty (world hand book of the educational organization statistics, 1998). Accordingly, it is revealed that there have been attempts to develop sports in countries like India, but due to poverty, many challenges and difficulties have been faced.

It is clear from the above information that various measures have been taken to develop the sport in Sri Lanka and in different countries of the world. It has been shown that motor activities are important from the pre-school stage in foreign countries. This shows the importance of developing sports, health and physical education in efforts to shape a person's character and acclimatize them to the living environment. Also, it is revealed from the above statements that the government has taken various steps to develop the sport by various institutions. The importance of developing sports more than other subjects in the school is because the personality that can enter the future world without fear can be obtained through sports. Also, in economically developed countries such as Britain, America and Japan, children are encouraged to play sports from a young age, and sports equipment, sports teachers, playgrounds, etc. have been developed for the development of sports. The skills of gifted students are further developed. Sports have become an essential part of socialist countries. Although there is a need to develop sports in developing countries like India and Sri Lanka, it is revealed that there are some difficulties in developing sports due to problems such as lack of teachers and sports equipment due to economic difficulties.

2.7 Actions Taken for Game Evaluation :

In schools, sports programs should be evaluated with the aim of producing a student with a balanced personality. Through this

section, it is studied how to evaluate sports programs in schools.

2014. As per circular ED 1 /15/2/ 4 /26 marks will be given in progress report book for sports in every school term examination. According to this school sports development program sports have been made compulsory for all students except disabled students. Accordingly, the students' sporting performance has been evaluated by giving marks to the progress report book for the term examination tests conducted at the end of each school term examination. Accordingly, it is clear that the Ministry of Education has taken measures to evaluate the game and awarding points for the game in the students. They can be described as a systematic assessment program launched in a way that provides context and motivation to play. As shown in the article Co-Curricular Activities in Sri Lanka (2011) Sports activities are often run under the co-curricular section of the school. There students can be motivated to develop their abilities by using different evaluation methods and determinants related to co-curricular activities. Among the ways that can be introduced

- Use of assessment methods and determinants.
- Pointed bending.
- color mastery,

At the end of the year prize giving ceremony, evaluations can be done at the school level such as certificates and trophies and prizes. Accordingly, it is clear that measures have been taken to systematically evaluate sports using the sports section under the co-curricular sections of the school. This shows that by taking these measures, it is possible to direct the student towards sports.

The skills of the students have been evaluated by awarding points for the sports championships of the students as follows.

All Sri Lanka Championship - 11 points

All Sri Lanka Sub-Championship – 10 points

District Championship – 9 points

District runner-up – 8 points

Staff Championship – 7 points

Staff runner-up – 6 points

Home Championship – 5 points

House Sub-Championship – 4 points

By assigning points for sports, it can be used as an evaluation to make students more interested in sports. Also, the students will be

able to give fame to the school at the national and international level and their educational activities will also be well supported.

Under the continuous assessment system for health and physical education subject of National General Certificate Examination, any mark for sports drill etc. was linked to the final mark of the students and therefore students participated enthusiastically in sports drills (National General Certificate Examination Proposed Plan, 1973). According to that, among the actions that were taken to evaluate the game in the early years, it seems that it is an important action that was taken in the evaluation of the game, which was linked to the final score in the general examination. Because of that, every student participated in the game showing interest and motivation for the game without discrimination, but there were educational differences. That situation has undergone changes nowadays.

As shown in the book Educational Science Research (2004), a uniform written test system limited to 3 hours is mostly used in the final examination of 6-11 years of secondary school in Sri Lanka. Practical tests are conducted in Music, Art. For several subjects like dance, home science etc

only Even so in the primary years. Subjects such as environmental studies, sports and aesthetics are continuously evaluated daily in the classroom and in the field based on the student's performance. According to this, it is clear that especially in primary education, sports have been evaluated through a mandatory screening of games for the primary years in order to get the fun etc. needed by the students.

The game has been evaluated in different ways in different countries. According to Manahara magazine (1987), in Japan, the government has taken steps to give priority in providing employment facilities to students who show special skills in sports than students who only study. Accordingly, it appears that the Japanese government has evaluated sports by providing employment opportunities to students with sports skills. Therefore, it is also clear that the participation of the students in the sports without distinction has happened because of the evaluation of the sports in this way.

Vosky (1995) points out that in Czechoslovakia, annual sports events that started at the school level have been extended

to the national level. Accordingly, it is seen how sports have been tried to be evaluated through holding sports events.

Annual sports events are held in public schools in India. Talented students are selected and given government scholarships etc. to advance them. Separate school sports have been started for students with sports talent. (world hand book of the educational organization statistics, 1998). According to this, it is clear that countries like India have also evaluated the game in the midst of many difficulties. This also reveals that sports have been evaluated by awarding scholarships to students who have sports skills.

In Germany, a child enters education at the age of 6. In the last year of primary school i.e. in year 10, a practical aptitude test is conducted for selection into sports. Those who pass the test are admitted to the sports club known as Sports School located in the district. Every district has such sports clubs and teaches their other subjects, but more attention is paid to sports. Those who fail for the first time in the examination conducted in the year 10 will be presented for the same examination within another 3 months. If you fail the same test for the second time The test is allowed for the third time also. For that, weak students are given special sports training and thirdly, students who pass are asked whether they have successfully studied other subjects (physical culture and sport in 1978, pp 27-28).

According to it is clear that in countries like Germany, it is revealed that the sport has been evaluated by periodically undergoing tests to measure the skill and checking whether the sports training has been successfully achieved. As with any classroom subject, sports education has 3 types of assessment of student achievement. Brajtu Webster describes these 3 assessment methods. That is, assessment for learning, formative assessment, summative assessment (Assessment for learning in physical education, 2017) and the following assessment methods for evaluating sports. can be used

- your wellness intelligence
- sample physical education participation and Effort record
- sample physical education teacher reflection/exit poll

- sample physical education Assessment tracking sheet (Assessment tools physical education, 2019).

From the above it is clear that various methods can be used to help evaluate the game.

Considering the above facts, it is clear that Sri Lanka has adopted different methods to evaluate sports in different countries. It seems that we have tried to develop the sports skills of students by establishing a suitable system for evaluating sports in our country from time to time. It is clear how important proposals for sports development under the continuous evaluation system were brought up but rejected as they were problematic in implementation.

The need for a formal evaluation system for sports has arisen in order to encourage them to return to sports, to develop their sports skills, to promote sports in the school and thereby produce a student with a balanced personality.

3. Methodology

The primary purpose of this research is to study how the evaluation system is implemented in schools and the problems that arise there, which is done by adding 100 points to the progress report book based on the sports activities for term exams in schools. In selecting the school sample for this study, 3 sports schools were selected from Western Province and using 1 school from Gampaha district, 1 school from Colombo district and 1 school from Kaluthara district. A total of 240 students and 18 sports teachers were used for this purpose, 10 students each from grades 8, 9, 10 and 11 from one school and 6 sports teachers from one school each. In launching this study, it was not possible to select the sample so that the sample is well representative of the relevant population in order to protect the external validity of the research. The sample is thus limited because for a large sample the commitment does not last long. The research instruments prepared here, questionnaires, were prepared according to the blueprint prepared in the preparation of the interview schedule. The Blueprints are given under the document. In this chapter, the research objectives are described again under sub-objectives and the method of conducting related research through the preparation of data collection equipment, the selection of the sample related to each objective, etc. has been described in this chapter.

3.1. Study Methodology

It also intends to follow the descriptive research method to study the performance of the game-based scoring system for the exams. As both quantitative data and qualitative data are used for this research, the data will be analyzed under mixed research methodology. That is, the data obtained from the questionnaires is done under quantitative data analysis methods and percentages, tables, graphs etc. are used for that. The information obtained from the interviews was used to analyze the data in depth and to describe the areas that were difficult to quantify. Thus, this research is conducted under mixed research methodology.

3.2 Explaining the research objectives

100 marks are added to the progress report book based on the game for term exams. At what level is the evaluation program being implemented in different schools and what are the problems in implementation?

The main objective is to study the functioning of game based scoring system for term tests in different schools. Following are the specific objectives set up to achieve this primary objective.

Specific Objectives

To review the Game-based scoring system for term tests in schools

1. To investigate the attitudes of sports teachers and students towards the performance of sport based scoring system for term tests in schools.
2. To study the problems faced by sports teachers in the implementation of Game-based scoring system for term tests in schools.
3. To study the problems and difficulties faced by the students while participating in Game-based scoring system for term tests.

These objectives are described in more detail here.

3.2.1. Awarding of marks based on sport for term examinations in schools

A balanced study of the manner in which the evaluation system operates. Under these objectives, questionnaires were given to physical education teachers to collect data. An interview was also conducted with physical education teachers. In order to verify the

authenticity of the information, interviews were conducted with students and PE teachers of the selected schools. Through the data obtained, it is hoped to study in a balanced way how this evaluation system is implemented in different schools. The following sub-objectives were used in preparing the questionnaires. For that

- To study what activities were used in the school to carry out the game-based assessment system,
- To study what sports are available in the school while choosing a sport,
- To study the adequacy of the physical resources required for the activities used to implement the game-based assessment system in the school
- Studying the current practice of game-based assessment in schools.
- To study the total amount of points given for evaluation on sports activities
- To study the criteria used for awarding points based on the game and the amount of points given to them.

Studying how Under the above objectives, the sports teachers and students will be interviewed in order to study how the sports-based evaluation system is being implemented in the school. An analysis is being done to find out how this works with diversity among schools and wait to analyze them in a balanced manner.

3.2.2. Investigate the attitudes of teachers and students towards the functioning of the game-based scoring system for term examinations in schools.

The main sample for data collection under these objectives were teachers and students not in charge of sports subject. Regarding the implementation of this game-based evaluation method, the teachers prepared a 10-statement Likert scale attitude test to test the attitudes of the students, in which 5 positive clauses and 5 negative clauses were included. While preparing those statements, their attitude towards the following sub-objectives was examined.

1. The assessment method called sport is an assessment of attitudes towards the importance of action in schools.

2. Examining existing attitudes towards the nature of performance of game-based assessment.
3. Examining the attitude test related to how the game-based assessment system affects the personality development of the students.
- 4 Examining the attitudes of students on the impact of the word-based evaluation method on the development of social skills.

3.2.3. To study the problems faced by the sports teachers in implementing the evaluation system of giving marks based on sports for term examinations in schools.

Under this objective, the sports teachers of the selected schools were used as the main sample used for data collection. Because they face great difficulties in implementing the sports-based assessment program. Data collection is done by giving a questionnaire to the sports teachers and conducting an interview with them. The issues that arise in the implementation of this game-based evaluation system are further explored in depth under the following sub-objectives.

- 1.To study the problems arising in relation to physical resources in the implementation of the sports-based assessment system,
- 2.To study the problems arising in relation to human resources in the implementation of sports-based evaluation system,
- 3.To study the financial problems that arise in the implementation of the evaluation system based on sports in the school,
- 4.To study the issues arising in relation to time management in implementing game based assessment system

3.2.4. To study the problems and difficulties faced by the students while participating in the game-based scoring system for term examinations in schools.

Under this objective, using students as the main criterion for data collection, the following sub-objectives will be prepared and a questionnaire will be used to study the problems and difficulties encountered by the students in participating in the sports-based evaluation program.

- 1.To study the issues that arise regarding students' interest in this game-based assessment.
- 2.To study the difficulties faced by students in participating in this game-based assessment program,

3.To study the problems arising in the implementation of game-based evaluation system in terms of scoring.

This research is launched through the above objectives and sub-objectives to find out how the game-based evaluation system works and the problems that arise during its implementation.

3.3. Study sample

3.3.1. How the research sample was selected

The primary objective here is to find out the status of the evaluation system of adding points to the students' progress report book for the semester exams by giving 100 points based on the game in schools, and to identify the problems that arise in the implementation, in order to achieve the objectives and sub-objectives. An investigation into how the sample was selected is expected here.

Western province sports schools was chosen for the selection of the sample. Among the provinces of sri lanka, this province was considered more appropriate as it has a moderate nature for sports as well as educational activities.

3.3.1.1.Target Population

The target population was all the sports schools in sri lanka but due to practical problems and time constraints it was difficult to select the relevant sample. Therefore, only 3 schools were selected as the sample among the schools in Western province..

The following sample was selected for this research from Western province. There are 27 Sports schools in Sri lanka. but, there are 3 schools were selected From each Districts of western province, under stratified random sampling method

01. How the sports teacher sample was selected

18 teachers were selected under simple random sampling with 6 sports teachers (e teachers and 3 coaches) each from one of the 3 selected schools.

02. How the teacher sample was selected

240 teachers were selected under simple random sampling, 80 teachers each from each of the 3 selected schools.

03. How the student sample was selected

240 students were selected under simple random sampling, 80 students each from each of the 3 selected schools from among the 8th,

9th, 10th, 11th grade students of the 3 selected schools.

3.3.2 How the sample was selected for collecting information under each objective

01. Sample selected for balanced study of functioning of sport based scoring system for term examinations in schools.

The sample used here is the selected sports schools in Western Province. 240 physical education and sports teachers were selected from 3 schools, 80 from each school. Out of the 240 physical education and sports teachers, one teacher from one school was used for interviews.

02. Selected sample to investigate teachers' and students' attitudes towards game-based scoring system for term examinations in schools.

Under this objective, information was collected using the following sample. Data was collected using 80 teachers from one school, 240 teachers from each school, and 240 students from grade 8, 9, 10, 11 from one school.

03. The sample selected to study the problems faced by sports teachers in the implementation of sports based scoring system for term examinations in schools.

6 sports teachers from each school and 80 other teachers from each schools, were selected as a total number of 18 sports teachers and 240 other teachers selected for this purpose. For this, data was collected through both sports teacher questionnaires and interviews.

04 Sample selected to study the problems and difficulties faced by students in participating in the game-based scoring system for term examinations in schools.

A total of 240 students were selected as a total sample of 20 students studying in one grade from 8, 9, 10, 11 each of the 3 schools selected.

3.4. Data Collection Devices

In order to achieve the intended objectives in this study, various measures were followed in developing the instruments used to obtain data so as to preserve its validity and reliability. Also to research. The examiner followed the methods of selecting the students in various ways, making the measuring instruments pre-tested, and minimizing the dropout of the test takers.

A blue map prepared to achieve the objectives and sub-objectives established for the launch of this study along with measures taken to achieve the respective objectives is given in Appendix ii.

3.4.1. Sports teacher and student interview schedule

From the 3 schools selected for the sample, 6 sports teachers, one teacher each in charge of physical education and sports, were used for the interview. For that, the interview schedule was prepared with 11 open questions and structured questions. Also, out of the 240 students selected from the 3 selected schools, two randomly selected students from each school were interviewed with 6 students each. For that, the interview schedule was prepared with 14 open questions and structured questions. Based on these 2 interviews, this evaluation will find out what activities are used to give 100 marks for the term exam based on sports activities and it is hoped to uncover the reasons for the activities that are mentioned in the circular document but are not used for evaluation. Also, the interview schedule directed questions to find out more about the available games for the students to choose a game to play in between the activities to give points based on the game. In addition to this, in order to get more details about the manner in which the sports-based evaluation system is implemented in the school, information such as the determinants used in giving marks to these sports activities and the problems that arise in the implementation of the sports-based evaluation system in the school and their solutions and plans are disclosed. Questions were directed by the interviewers for taking.

3.4.2. Sports Teacher Quiz

Presently, in order to examine how the evaluation system of giving 100 marks based on sports for the term examination in schools is working, a questionnaire was given to the sports teachers of the three selected schools, how this evaluation is currently being implemented, and the activities that exist in the schools to evaluate the students and their Whether there are adequate facilities and whether they are available, the training that supervises the awarding of marks and conducts the awarding of marks

Part 1 of the 7-question questionnaire is given to the sports teachers to obtain data on the format, the criteria used for awarding marks, and the manner in which marks are reported. Part 2 of this questionnaire uncovered many other issues.

3.4.3 Student Questionnaire

This questionnaire consists of two parts and part 1 is used to ask teachers' and students' attitudes towards game-based assessment. The questions in Part 2 were used to uncover the problems students encountered in participating in the game-based assessment. There, the students will get data about the difficulties that arise in this regard and the solutions to those problems will also be revealed through this questionnaire.

3.4.4 Attitude scales

In order to know the attitude of other teachers and students who are not teachers in charge of the sports subject regarding the operation of the evaluation system based on sports for the term examination, an attitude test was conducted using positive and negative statements. 240 teachers and 240 students were selected. Here, in order to measure their response to the game-based evaluation system, this was compiled in a way that contains responses in 5 categories according to the Likert scale.

Here, 5 anti-genetic clauses were used and points were assigned as follows for the responses given regarding its statements.

TABLE 3.4.4-1 - SCORING SCALE FOR POSITIVE STATEMENTS

Highly agree	-2
Agree	-1
Moderate	0
Don't agree	1
Totally disagree	2
Highly agree	-2
Agree	-1
Moderate	0
Disagree	1
Strongly disagree	2

TABLE 3.4.4-2 - SCORING SCALE FOR NEGATIVE STATEMENTS

Also, 5 negative clauses were used and the following points were assigned for the responses given regarding the statements.

3.5 How Data Analysis Is Performed

The data analysis work is done under mixed research methodology. For that, data analysis is done using statistical methods such as percentages, table graphs etc.

Under the first objective, the data obtained from the questionnaires are organized and analyzed using tables, and the data obtained from the interviews are analyzed using

qualitative analysis methods to describe the required data in depth.

Under the second objective, the data obtained from the questionnaires are organized and analyzed using percentage tables and graphs, and under the third objective, the data obtained from the 11th section of the questionnaire of sports teachers are organized and analyzed using percentages and ratios, and qualitative analysis methods are used to analyze the objective in depth. .

Under the fourth objective, the data obtained from the questionnaires are organized and analyzed using percentages and tables. It identified the problems that arise when

students participate in the game-based assessment system.

In this way, the analysis is done using quantitative and qualitative data analysis methods.

3.6 Limitations of the Study

In this study, the focus is on studying the nature of the sports-based evaluation system for the term examinations of a few schools selected under stratified random sampling in Sitawaka Division, Homagama region, according to the plan issued by the Ministry of Education for the implementation of sports-based evaluation in schools. Although this evaluation system is not functioning properly, it is a problem that exists throughout Sri Lanka. This does not include a range. Because it is done by a single person and there is not enough time for it, considering the cost to be incurred for it, as above, this study is limited to only a few schools in Seethawaka division of Homagama region.

In this study, we only study how the game-based evaluation system works in different schools and the problems that arise during the implementation, and how the marks obtained by students based on these games affect their educational performance is not studied here. The information available on this is limited as there is a problem of not being able to properly implement this evaluation system in schools due to the fact that teachers who are not rural education subjects in schools are in charge of the sports department. Also, this game-based study may not generalize to the entire school system.

5. Results and Discussion

4.1. How the game-based scoring system works for term examinations in schools.

Under this objective, 2 main samples were used to collect data and questionnaires and interviews were used to collect data. Several research questions were used in preparing the questionnaire. The sample used here was 6 sports teachers from one school and 2 students from each of the selected schools were selected for interviews. Here the attention is paid to the following aspects.

- 1) Used in school to conduct game based assessment system activities,
- 2) In choosing and doing any sport, the school has facilities for it Sports
- 3) Adequacy of physical resources required for the activities used to implement the game-based assessment system in the school.
- 4) Game-based assessment system in current form in schools
- 5) Total points awarded for evaluation based on sports activities
- 6) Scores awarded based on the game criteria and them
- 7) How to record attendance and scores in the Game Based Evaluation System.

4.1.1. Activities used in schools to implement the game-based assessment system

Here, data was collected from the sports teachers through a questionnaire and an interview, and the students were interviewed to verify the correctness of the conditions. The three schools chosen for the convenience of balanced analysis are Gampaha district sports school, Colombo district Sports school, Kaluthara district sports school, named and analyzed as The data obtained from the questionnaires are shown in the table below

TABLE 4.1.1-1 - THE GAME-BASED ASSESSMENT SYSTEM WAS USED IN SCHOOLS

Activity	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Total sample	
				Quantity	Percentage (%)
Practice a selected sport	6	6	6	18	100
Scout	6	6	6	18	100
Cadets	6	6	6	18	100
General fitness	-	6	-	6	33.3
Sport activities organized by school	6	6	6	18	100

For this question, the circular issued by the Ministry of Education has presented the 5 activities mentioned in the evaluation, where it appears that the activity of practicing a certain sport is used in the schools and marks are given for this evaluation. It is clear from the fact that 18 sports teachers in each school have responded. From the student interviews, it is revealed that according to the facilities available in the school, various sports are used to give marks. Apart from School, it seems that only Colombo school have used the physical fitness program to give marks for this assessment. Also, it appears that the physical fitness activity has not been used for this evaluation method in Gampaha and Kaluthara school. The student interviews revealed that they show an interest in physical fitness. But this reveals that the school has not given the opportunity for that. The reason for that was revealed in the interview that since the school is a sports school, more attention is given only to sports and not much attention is given to physical health. According to this, it is clear that physical fitness, which is a fundamental element of sports, is not used in this school, but the literature research revealed that more attention has been given to physical fitness in sports activities in countries such as America, China, and Czechoslovakia. It was revealed that there is a vacancy for properly trained teachers to conduct Morning physical fitness sessions.

All 3 schools indicate the scout and cadets, but the students are not awarded points for their participation. During the student interviews, it was also revealed that according to the competitions, different people, first aid programs etc. are implemented

Also, all 3 schools indicate that the sports activities organized by the school are implemented according to the seasons of each school, but the students are not awarded points for their participation. During the student

interviews, it was also revealed that according to the seasons, different people, first aid programs etc. are implemented

But for that, marks are not awarded for participating in it. Accordingly, it is revealed that some activities are implemented, but an evaluation is made for them and marks are not awarded to the student. In addition to this, the 3 schools conduct inter-house sports competitions, divisional sports competitions, regional sports competitions, district sports competitions, provincial sports competitions, participation in all-Ceylon and international waves, giving points for achievement levels and getting 1st, 2nd, 3rd place in those competitions. Indicated that marks are awarded to students instead of representation. In order to verify the correctness of the scoring, it was revealed in the interviews that the sports teachers are marking the achievement in the sports book and giving them a score. But the students said that the sports teacher had to constantly remind them to get those marks.

Through this, this evaluation system is carried out through various activities in different schools and not even one school uses all the 5 activities specified by the ministry and according to the amount of resources and facilities available to the schools, these activities are used more or less and this evaluation system is implemented. Information has been revealed.

4.1.2. In choosing and doing any sport in the sports school where there are facilities for it

The following table shows the responses given by the sports teachers to the question which sports have been given to you to choose from the school in giving the opportunity to the student to choose a particular sport.

TABLE 4.1.2-1 - WHILE CHOOSING ANY SPORT AND DOING IT, THE SPORTS FOR WHICH THE SCHOOL HAS FACILITIES

Sport	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Total sample	
				Quantity	Percentage (%)
1. Cricket	6	6	6	18	100
2. Football	6	6	6	18	100
3. Athletes	6	6	6	18	100
4. Netball	6	6	6	18	100
5. Rugger	-	6	6	12	66.6
6. Chess	6	6	6	18	100

7. Volleyball	6	6	6	18	100
8. Other	6	6	6	18	100

Here it is clear that cricket, football, athletics, netball, Chess and volleyball among the sports that can be chosen by the students during the selection of certain sports have been selected and used for training in each school. Its percentage is 100%. Olombo and Kaluthara schools only have the Rugger game and its percentage is 66.66 %. It is revealed that no Gampaha school has given students an opportunity to choose rugger.

It is special that the game of rugby was not used as a sport of choice for the students for this evaluation system in any other school except in the Colombo and Kaluthara school. Interviews revealed that the reason for not implementing it in other schools is that there are few trainers. It was also revealed that the game of rugby was not used to give points due to the increase in the number of accidents caused to students by this game.

It is noteworthy that no school has used checkers to score points for this evaluation system. But except the chess game all schools with a response of 70, it is clear that in all other schools students have been given the opportunity to choose this game for scoring. It appears that carrom is also not given an opportunity to be selected for this evaluation system in all schools except in Colombo school. Accordingly, one of the things revealed here is that schools often give more opportunities for

field sports, but less opportunities are given for indoor sports, and in addition to this, wrestling, kabaddi, boxing, karate and other competitive sports are used to give points in the Colombo school. And also all schools give the opportunity to choose to give marks to students for all sports.

It was revealed from the interviews. As a whole, this reveals that Colombo and Kaluthara school plays every game except the chain game, more than other schools. Student interviews also revealed that scores are given by playing each of those games.

4.1.3. Adequacy of physical resources required for the activities used to implement the game-based assessment system in the school

The responses given by the sports teachers to the question of how much physical resources are required for the activities used to implement the sports-based evaluation system in the school are as follows.

TABLE 4.1.3-1 - ADEQUACY OF PHYSICAL RESOURCES REQUIRED FOR THE ACTIVITIES USED TO IMPLEMENT THE GAME-BASED ASSESSMENT SYSTEM IN THE SCHOOL

	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Total sample	
				Quantity	Percentage (%)
Very enough	-	-	-	-	-
enough	-	-	-	-	-
Not enough	6	6	6	18	100
Too much is not enough	-	-	-	-	-

Here the sports teachers of all schools have given the answer that they are not enough for this and the percentage is 100%. All schools are sports school, all the resources required by the state have been not provided, indicating that the available physical resources are not sufficient for the implementation of this evaluation system. The sports teacher of Gampaha school gave an interview, "Even

though it is a national school, the sports equipment does not come, but the equipment comes to the sports schools anyway. Our schools have gone to all Sri Lanka and won, but the school does not even have 10 nets, 6 hurdles and the rest are running with 8 chairs. The sports teacher of the school gave the interviews with the few resources and they said small schools have not enough facilities.

It's like sports schools sell them when they find gems and polish them. We keep the resources there and we take advantage of the children who are training hard without any resources." According to these statements in the interviews, it is revealed that the resources are divided between the schools due to the lack of sufficient facilities in other schools except the high schools. It is revealed that there is a disparity in going and that these divisions have strongly affected the internal sports activities.

4.1.4. Game-based assessment system in current form in schools.

Regarding the nature of the sports-based scoring system for the term exams, information was revealed in the following tables given in the sports teacher questionnaire in the study and data was collected through in-depth interviews. The following tables show the number of days, hours, hours of operation and monitoring of this evaluation in schools.

TABLE 4.1.4-1 - THE NUMBER OF DAYS THE GAME-BASED ASSESSMENT SYSTEM IS CURRENTLY BEING IMPLEMENTED IN SCHOOLS

Activity	Hours			Days		
	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara
Practice a selected sport	2	2	2	2	1	1
Scout	2	2	2	1	1	2
Cadets	3	2	2	3	3	2
Morning General Fitness	-	20 Min	-	-	2	-
Sport Activities organized by school	2	1	1	2	1	2

FIGURE 1 - THE NUMBER OF DAYS THE GAME BASED ASSEMENT SYSTEM IS CURRENTLY BEING IMPLEMENTED IN SCHOOLS

TABLE 4.1.4-2 - THE NUMBER OF DAYS THE GAME-BASED ASSESSMENT SYSTEM IS CURRENTLY BEING IMPLEMENTED IN SCHOOLS

Activity	Hours						Days					
	1		2		3		1		2		3	
Practice a selected sport	-	-	18	100%	-	-	12	66.6%	6	33.3%	-	-
Scout	-	-	18	100%	-	-	12	66.6%	6	33.3%	-	-
Cadets	-	-	12	66.6%	6	33.3%	-	-	6	33.3%	12	66.6%
Morning General Fitness	6 (20 min)	33.3%	-	-	-	-	-	-	6	33.3%	-	-
Sport Activities organized by school	12	66.6%	6	33.3%	-	-	6	33.3%	12	66.6%	-	-

According to the table above, it is possible to reveal the form of the game-based instruction system currently being implemented in schools. There, All schools conduct sports training 5 days a week when choosing any sport. But in addition to all 5 days a week, even on holidays, sports training is implemented for this evaluation, so more time for sports. But only colombo schools conducting morning physical fitness programme in two days of week. Being reserved can be described as a good condition. It appears that the student does reed training only 01 day a week even in the 5 days of the less skilled activities of the school. It is revealed that Colombo school's physical health is done 2 days per week .So, Colombo school

becomes the school that uses more days of the week for physical health.

In the implementation of this sports-based evaluation system in different schools, the number of hours of training per day for selecting a particular sport and practicing it is equal to 2 or 3 hours. Gampaha school has more training hours and days compared to other schools. Also, it is clear that in the physical health of the school, maintain a good level.

TABLE 4.1.4-4 - TIME AND MONITORING OF CURRENT IMPLEMENTATION OF GAME-BASED ASSESSMENT SYSTEM IN SCHOOLS OF AFFAIRS

Activity	Time			Supervise		
	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara
Practice a selected sport	After & Before School	After & Before School	After & Before School	Teacher	Teacher	Teacher
Scout	After/ Before School & On time	After/ Before School & On time	After/ Before School & On time	Teacher	Teacher	Teacher
Cadets	After & Before School	After & Before School	After & Before School	Teacher	Teacher	Teacher
Morning General Fitness	-	On Time	-	-	Teacher	-
Sport Activities organized by school	After School	After School	After School	Teacher	Teacher	Teacher

Activity	Time			Supervise	
	Before	After	On Time	Couch	Teacher
Practice a selected sport	18	18	-	-	18
Scout	18	18	18	-	18
Cadets	18	18	-	-	18
Morning General Fitness	-	6	-	-	6

Sport Activities organized by school	-	18	18	-	18
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In the study of how the sports-based evaluation system is implemented in the school, it is clear from the responses of the sports teachers about the time of practice of those activities that a certain sport is chosen and practice is mostly done before the school starts and after the school ends in all the four schools. that will Colombo school, It is

revealed that each school conducts only physical fitness activities during school hours and does not use the time available for learning in school for sports training activities. Therefore, it is found that the game-based evaluation system is implemented in a way that does not interfere with the students' educational activities.

FIGURE 2 - TIME AND MONITORING OF CURRENT IMPLEMENTATION OF GAME BASED ASSESSMENT SYSTEM IN SCHOOLS OF AFFAIRS

Also, these activities are done by the sports subject teacher in each school in terms of monitoring and giving marks. Although the support of not only the sports teachers of the school but also the class teachers are used to monitor the evaluation activities, it is revealed that the class teachers are not contacted to monitor the evaluation activities of other schools. Accordingly, compared to other schools, it is revealed that school is doing these evaluation activities in cooperation. Accordingly, in the study of the manner in which the sports-based evaluation system is implemented in these three schools, it is revealed how the sports school is implemented

in a formal manner compared to other schools. This is confirmed because this school conducts training for 2 hours even on holidays and gives more attention to sports. He also said that each school will be training on the week days of the sports. Also, it was revealed in the interviews that the sports activities organized by the school in every school are not implemented according to a daily schedule and are organized at different times according to the need. Overall, it is revealed that every school has prepared an action program that is implemented daily.

4.1.5. Games activities on a Total marks awarded for evaluation

TABLE 4.1.5-1 - THE TOTAL NUMBER OF POINTS AWARDED FOR EVALUATION IS BASED ON SPORTS ACTIVITIES

	District			Total Sample	
	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Quantity	Percentage %
200	-	-	-	-	-
150	-	-	-	-	-
100	6	6	6	18	100%
50	-	-	-	-	-

In question 5 of this questionnaire, which is the total number of points given to the student in this game-based evaluation system, the answer given by all the four schools is 100 points, so the percentage is 100%. Accordingly, this explains that each school will give 100 marks for this game-based evaluation system. Accordingly, it is clear that even though the Ministry of Education has not used all the activities mentioned in the circular issued regarding this evaluation system, it is

revealed that every school has worked to give the amount of 100 marks recommended by the Ministries.

4.1.6. Referees used for the game-based evaluation system and the amount of points awarded to them

TABLE 4.1.6-1 - THE DATA WAS ANALYZED BY THE FOLLOWING TABLE OF POINTS GIVEN FOR THE ACTIVITIES USED IN THE GAME-BASED ASSESSMENT SYSTEM.

	District			Yes/No			
	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Yes		No	
Practice a selected sport	80	80	100	18	100%	-	-
Scout	-	-	-	-	-	18	100%
Cadets	-	-	-	-	-	18	100%
Morning General Fitness	-	20	-	6	33.3%	12	66.6%
Sport Activities organized by school	20	-	-	6	33.3%	12	66.6%
Total Marks	100	100	100				

All the 3 schools indicate the participation and active contribution of the students as the leader and in addition, the attendance of 240 students in the school in 148 and in addition the need to pass a practical test was used as a leader. That was confirmed according to the information obtained from the interviews. It was also revealed in the student interviews that the students get these points after facing a practical test for the sport they are practicing. Accordingly, it is revealed that the method of giving marks to the students of all schools are same.

100 marks will be given by participating in a practical test for choosing a sport in Gampaha and colombo schools and 80 marks and Kaluthara school give 100 marks for practicing any sport. In colombo school give 20 marks for physical fitness activities. In Gampaha school total of 100 marks is awarded with 80 marks for practice of any sport, 20 marks for

sporting activities organized by school. A total of 100 marks will be awarded by colombo school with 80 marks for practice selected sports and 20 marks for physical fitness activities, A total of 100 marks will be awarded by Kaluthara school with 100 marks for practice selected sports.

In addition to this, in the interviews, as another determinant used in giving points for this evaluation system in all these 3 schools, in an inter-house sports representation, 7, 6, 5 points are given respectively for places 1.2.3 and 4 points are given for representation. Also, 11, 10, and 9 points will be given for the places 1.2.3 and 8 points for the representation of the division. 15, 14, 13 points will be given for 1st, 2nd, 3rd place in regional games and 12 points will be given for regional representation. 109 8 marks will be given for places 1, 2.3 respectively and 7 marks will be given for a district representation. 15, 14, 13

points will be awarded for the 1st, 2nd, 3rd positions respectively, 12 points will be given at the provincial performance level and 11 points will be given for a provincial representation. Also, 13, 12, 11 points are given for the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd places for All Sri Lanka and 10 points for the All Sri Lankan representation, 15 points for participating in international competitions and 14 points for reaching the All Sri Lankan performance level.

Thus, it appears that students are given marks for representing themselves through playing, winning competitions in 1st, 2nd, 3rd places, etc., and reaching achievement levels. But in the student interviews, it was revealed that many students are not aware of this kind of

scoring system and therefore they are less likely to participate in regional, district and all-Ceylon competitions. The sports teachers are reminded to collect these marks for the students appearing for these existing competitions. Accordingly, it is revealed that the students have not been properly informed about the marks given for regional, district and all-Ceylon competitions.

4.1.7. How to Record Attendance and Marks in the Game Based Assessment System

TABLE 4.1.7-1 - HOW TO RECORD ATTENDANCE AND MARKS IN GAME BASED EVALUATION SYSTEM

	District			Total sample	
	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Quantity	Percentage
Card	-	-	-	-	-
Notebook	-	-	-	-	-
Record book	6	6	6	18	100%
Sign sheet	-	-	-	-	-

For question 7 of the Sports Teacher Questionnaire, How are scores recorded in the sports-based scoring system for the portal exams, all three schools indicated that scoring for this evaluation is done by maintaining a record book of sports activities.

The interviews revealed that the sports teachers record the scores and give them to the class teacher at the end and add the scores to the progress report book. In addition, interviews revealed that students' attendance is recorded daily using a signature register. Accordingly, as shown above, it is possible to analyze in a balanced manner the way in which the sports-based evaluation system is implemented in different schools.

4.2. Attitudes of teachers and students towards game-based scoring system for term examinations in schools

The main sample used for data collection under the above purpose was 210 teachers and 210 students who are not in charge of sports subjects in the selected schools. A

questionnaire containing 5 positive and negative statements each was given for their opinion. There, their attitude towards the following aspects was examined.

1. Attitudes towards the importance of implementing game-based assessment in schools.
2. Prevailing attitude towards the nature of performance of game-based assessment system
3. Attitudes related to how the game-based assessment system affects the personality development of students
4. Attitudes about how game-based assessment affects the development of students' social skills

4.2.1. Teachers' and students' perceptions of the game-based scoring system for term exams.

TABLE 4.2.1-1 - TEACHERS' AND STUDENTS' COUNTER-COGNITIVE ATTITUDES TOWARDS GAME-BASED SCORING SYSTEM FOR TERM EXAMS.

Positive attitudes	Highly Appreciated		Appreciated		Moderate		Disagree		Strongly disagree		Total Marks	
	Teacher	Student	Teacher	Student	Teacher	Student	Teacher	Student	Teacher	Student	Teacher	Student
This evaluation system helps the physical and mental development of the student	208	180	2	30	-	-	-	-	-	-	418 (99.5%)	390 (92.9%)
This evaluation system will help to improve the sports skills of every student who is good and unfit for sports.	184	150	16	22	10	38	-	-	-	-	384 (91.4%)	322 (76.7%)
Through this evaluation system points are given for the sports, thus creating motivation to engage with sports	195	201	11	8	4	1	-	-	-	-	401 (95.5%)	412 (98.1%)
Leadership skills are developed through this evaluation system	187	179	13	-	10	31	-	-	-	-	387 (92.1%)	358 (85.2%)
Through this evaluation system, qualities like cooperation, tolerance, unity are developed	210	170	-	-	-	40	-	-	-	-	420 (100%)	340 (80.9%)

Graphs showing teachers' and students' cognitive attitudes of game-based scoring system for term exams

FIGURE 3 - TEACHERS' & STUDENTS' COGNITIVE ATTITUDES OF GAME BASED SCORING SYSTEM

According to the graph and table above, the opinions expressed by students and teachers regarding the 5 reproductive statements can be analyzed as follows.

210 teachers and 210 students participate in providing the above responses. According to the teachers and the range of marks of the students spans between +420 to 420. All in relation to a publication If people show high agreement. A value of +420 does not agree at all If -420 value should also be obtained.

418 marks for teachers and 390 marks students have expressed agreement with a high level of agreement for the statement that this evaluation method, which is the first statement among regenerative methods, helps the physical and mental development of the student. Looking at this as a percentage, teachers and students have expressed agreement with a high percentage of 99.5% and 92.9% respectively. Accordingly, 100 students said that sports help in the physical and mental development of students

It is shown that teachers accept both groups and have a positive attitude about it. The second reproducible statement is that this evaluation method helps to develop the sports skills of every student, whether gifted or not. For the statement, teachers have expressed agreement by getting a mark of 384 and students a mark of 322 and as a percentage 91 4% of teachers and 77% of students expressed agreement. According to this It is clear that the teachers have a good attitude about this compared to the students.

The third statement among the regenerative statements is given a mark through this evaluation system, so the student is motivated to play, for the statement that 401 teachers and 412 students scored a high level of agreement. Looking at this as a percentage, teachers and students have expressed agreement with a high percentage of 95.5% and 98.1% of the answers. It is clear that both students and teachers accept that giving points has been a very good basis for directing the game, and that they have a positive attitude about it.

The fourth regenerative statement, leadership skills are formed through this evaluation

method, means that 387 teachers and 358 students have expressed agreement with the statement and 92.1% of teachers and students have expressed agreement with a percentage of 85.2%. According to this, it is clear that the teachers have a good attitude about this compared to the students and at the same time it is accepted that this evaluation system leads to the development of leadership skills by both the teachers and the students.

The last statement among the regenerative statements, the student's qualities such as cooperation, tolerance, and unity are developed through this evaluation method, although teachers showed the highest agreement with a maximum score of 420, but the students expressed agreement by obtaining a score of 340. Looking at this as a percentage, 100% of teachers and students agreed and 80.9% agreed. This implies that there is a maximum positive attitude of teachers than students towards the development of social skills. However, it is clear that both students and teachers accept this and have a positive attitude towards it.

According to the presentation and interpretation of the data collected from the responses given by the students and teachers regarding the above five racist statements, it is clear that there is a good attitude towards this evaluation method in both the teachers and students. For the fifth statement, the teachers strongly agreed with 100% and for the other four statements, more than 90% of the teachers agreed with those statements. Students also agreed with Amy's statements with over 75% responding to the five statements. No negative value was obtained for any statement and all parties agreed more than 75% on each statement, confirming that non- sport teachers and students in sports schools have positive attitudes towards reproductive statements.

FIGURE 4 - CORRELATION OF TEACHERS' & STUDENTS' POSITIVE ATTITUDES

Significant value of this two variables of teachers' positive attitudes and students' positive attitudes is

		TEACHER	STUDENT
TEACHER	Pearson Correlation	1	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001
	N	210	210
STUDENT	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	
	N	210	210

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

0.001. According to pearson correlation, since this significant value is between 0 – (+1) it is clear that there is a positive relationship between these two variables. But it is a positive weak correlation Because Sig value is near to 0. That is, there is an inverse relationship between teachers' and students' attitudes about positive attitudes.

4.2.2. Negative attitudes of teachers and students towards game-based scoring system for term exams.

TABLE 4.2.2-1 - NEGATIVE ATTITUDES OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS TOWARDS GAME-BASED SCORING SYSTEM FOR TERM EXAMS.

Negative attitudes	Highly Appreciated		Appreciated		Moderate		Disagree		Strongly disagree		Total Marks	
	Teacher	Student	Teacher	Student	Teacher	Student	Teacher	Student	Teacher	Student	Teacher	Student
Time spent on this evaluation method is a waste of time.	55	-	58	11	28	52	43	61	26	106	-73 (17.4%)	222 (2.4%)
This evaluation system is a hindrance to the completion of the prescribed curriculum in the school	-	-	33	15	38	30	108	119	31	46	137 (32.6%)	196 (46.7%)
This evaluation method does not contribute to produce a person with a balanced personality	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11	210	199	420 (100%)	409 (97.4%)
The time spent on this assessment method is more effective if it is used for learning in the classroom	86	76	43	40	28	41	20	21	33	32	-129 (30.7%)	-107 (25.5%)

Since this evaluation system is conducted in the evening, students are prone to un-necessary things	122	60	37	24	40	49	7	7	4	70	-266 (-63.4%)	3 (0.71%)
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The assignment of points for the above expressions ranges between -420 and +420. A score of -420 should be obtained if all students or teachers strongly agree with a statement, and +420 if they do not agree at all.

In order to find out whether non- sports teachers and students have a negative attitude towards this game- based assessment method, five negative attitudes were presented to which 210 students and 210 teachers responded.

For the negative attitude that the evaluation is a waste of time, the teachers' responses have a score of -73, which is a percentage of -17.4% who agree with this statement. But according to student responses, 222 students have obtained marks for it, which is a percentage of 52.9%. Accordingly, the students have not expressed their agreement to this statement. Accordingly, it is revealed that although the teachers accept this evaluation system as a waste of time, the students do not accept it. That is, teachers have a bad attitude about this and students have a good attitude. This suggests that teachers' attitudes towards play should be developed to make teachers understand that play is not a waste of time and that it is important to allocate time for the student to play.

The response of both the teachers and students to the second negative statement that this evaluation system hinders the completion of the school's prescribed curriculum is positive. That is, 137 and 196 of the responses given by teachers and students have a positive mark. It is 32.6% and 46.7% of the answers. That is, the majority of non- sports teachers and students in the sample do not agree with this statement and thus it is revealed that this evaluation method does not hinder the completion of the prescribed curriculum.

The third of the negative statements is that this assessment method does not contribute to producing a person with a balanced personality. All the teachers have not agreed to

that and the vast majority of the students have not agreed to it at all. According to that, the teachers get the maximum 420 points and 100% highest percentage, and the students get 409 points and 97.4% disagree. This implies that the sport contributes in producing a person with a balanced personality and it is very satisfactory to have a good attitude about it in both the teachers and students.

The time spent on this assessment method is more effective if it is used for classroom learning. Teachers and students agree on the fourth objection statement. Here, teachers had more agreement than students and it score of -127. Percentage wise -30.7%. According to the students' responses to that statement, students scored -107 or -25.5%. Accordingly, it is clear that teachers and students have a negative attitude towards this statement. That is, the teachers and students admitting that the time spent on this evaluation system will be more effective if it is used for classroom learning, it is revealed that there is a negative aspect towards this evaluation system.

As this evaluation system is conducted in the evening, there is a risk of inducing students to commit wrongdoing. In the last negative expression, it can be recognized that the opinions of students and teachers are different from each other. For this, students are given 3 marks for the given responses. Accordingly, 0.71% of students do not agree with this statement. But according to the teachers, by responding in a percentage of -266 or -63.3%, it has been accepted that there is a risk of tempting students to do wrong actions by implementing this evaluation system in the evening. Accordingly, it is clear that there is an opposite attitude regarding this attitude among students and teachers. That is, it is revealed that there is a negative attitude and a positive attitude towards this statement.

FIGURE 5 - TEACHERS' & STUDENTS' NEGATIVE ATTITUDES OF GAME-BASED SCORING SFOR TERM EXAMS

According to the graph above, among the negative attitudes, teachers have a negative attitude towards the first, fourth and fifth attitudes, but students have a negative attitude only towards the fourth attitude. With the first and last statements, the students responded positively while the teachers responded negatively. Both parties disagreed and gave positive responses to the second and third publications. Overall, according to the graph and table, it is revealed that teachers and

students have both good and bad attitudes towards this evaluation method. Therefore, it is clear that the attitude of teachers and students should be developed regarding this game-based evaluation system.

FIGURE 6 - CORRELATION OF TEACHERS' & STUDENTS' NEGATIVE ATTITUDES

Significant value of this two variables of teachers' negative attitudes and students' negative attitudes

		TEACHER	STUDENT
TEACHER	Pearson Correlation	1	-.211**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	210	210
STUDENT	Pearson Correlation	-.211**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	210	210

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

is 0.002. According to pearson correlation, since this significant value is between 0 – (+1) it is clear that there is a positive relationship between these two variables. But it is a positive weak correalation Because Sig value

is near to 0. That is, there is an inverse relationship between teachers' and students' negative attitudes.

		TEACHER	STUDENT
TEACHER	Pearson Correlation	1	-.191**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.006
	N	210	210
STUDENT	Pearson Correlation	-.191**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	
	N	210	210

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

FIGURE 7 - CORRELATION OF TEACHERS' & STUDENTS' OVERALL ATTITUDES

When measuring the relationship between the overall attitude level of teachers and students about this game-based evaluation method, it is clear that it is an inverse relationship. That is, the value of that relationship is 0.006. According to Pearson correlation, since this significant value is between 0 – (+1) it is clear that there is a positive relationship between these two variables. But it is a positive weak correlation because the Sig value is near to 0. That is, there is an inverse relationship between teachers' and students' full attitudes.

4.3. Problems faced by sports teachers in implementing sports based scoring system for term examinations in schools.

I choosed 18 sports teachers from the three schools selected for this as the main target. Data was collected by giving questionnaires to 6 sports teachers from each school, And to study these issues in depth Among the selected sports teachers, one sports teacher from each school was interviewed.

Here, the problems in implementing the sports-based evaluation system for sports

teachers were discussed in several areas. There.

1. Regarding physical resources in the implementation of the sports-based assessment system Emerging issues.
2. Issues arising in relation to human resources in the implementation of game-based evaluation system
3. Financial problems arising in the implementation of the evaluation system based on sports in the school
4. Time management in the implementation of game based evaluation system Problems arising in relation to

4.3.1. Physical problems arising in the implementation of the game-based scoring system for term examinations in schools.

TABLE 4.3.1-1 - PHYSICAL PROBLEMS ARISING IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE EVALUATION SYSTEM OF GIVING MARKS FOR TERM EXAMS BASED ON SPORTS.

Physical problems	District			Yes / No		Total
	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Yes	No	
Absence of spacious playground and sports stadium.	4	4	3	11	7	61.1%
Absence of necessary equipments and buildings	4	5	3	12	6	66.6%
Not enough physical resources	6	6	6	18	-	100%

In the study of the problems of sports teachers in relation to physical resources, 100% of sports teachers in schools stated that the physical resources required for sports were not sufficient. According to answers all teachers highly faced that problem. But it is clear from the fact that 66.6% responded that the second main problem related to the instruments and buildings availability. Colombo schools have the lack of problems about equipments and buildings for sports. Sports teachers showed sports equipment during the interviews

Due to non-availability, equipments and other aids are used instead of sports equipment during the competitions and training of the students. schools not having a playground and a sports stadium with the necessary space is a problem for all schools, it is clear that it is a problem for the sports teachers of all schools. During the interviews, it was revealed that playgrounds with a large area are available for urban schools and the playgrounds of rural schools are not prepared in such a way that they can be used properly. In the study of the entire sample of teachers on problems related

to physical resources, it is clear that it is a major problem for both types of schools with 100% responding to the problems of lack of physical resources required for sports. Accordingly, it is clear that there is a problem regarding physical resources for Gampaha, Colombo and Kaluthara schools and it is revealed that these problems face more in all schools.

4.3.2. Issues arising in relation to human resources in the implementation of game-based evaluation system.

Questions 10 to 13 of the Sports Teacher Questionnaire were presented to address the issues arising from insufficient human resources in implementing the sports-based scoring system for term examinations. The responses given by the sports teachers are as follows.

TABLE 4.3.2-1 - HUMAN RESOURCE ISSUES IN IMPLEMENTING GAME-BASED ASSESSMENT SYSTEM.

Human resources related problems	District			Yes / No		Total
	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Yes	No	
Not sufficient sports teachers	3	4	4	11	7	61.1%
Not sufficient coaches and sports teachers	4	5	5	14	4	77.7%
Lack of support from class teachers to supervise in giving marks for sports activities	3	2	4	9	9	50%
Parents and other subject teachers do not support the implementation of this evaluation system	4	2	4	10	8	55.5%

In the study of the problems of sports teachers in relation to human resources, it is revealed that the lack of sports coaches and sports instructors as a major problem for Colombo and Kaluthara schools is the lack of sports coaches and sports instructors. The same problem has become the main problem in

Gampaha schools and 4 responses have been given for it. In addition, 3 responses from Gampaha schools and 4 responses from Colombo and Kaluthara schools for the problem of not having enough sports teachers, so it is stronger for Gampaha schools than other schools. Covers that there has been a

problem. During the interviews, it was revealed that the number of coaches is very less and they are contacted externally for their school's sports activities. There, the sports teacher of Gampaha school said in the interviews, "if sports coaches who are experts in each sports subject are given, we can be more successful because, football coach cannot be coached in karate without knowledge". It is necessary to get successful results. Total number of all schools. In the study, it is revealed that it is a strong problem for all schools by having a percentage of 77% for the problem of not having enough sports coaches and sports instructors. Accordingly, this reveals that the school system itself needs the necessity of sports coaches who are experts in sports subjects.

50% sports teachers in schools responded to the problems of parents and other subject teachers not supporting the implementation of this evaluation system, while 9 of sports teachers in schools responded less. Accordingly, it is revealed that it has become a problem for sports teachers in Kaluthara schools more than in Gampaha and Colombo schools. In the interview, it was further revealed that the parents also express their displeasure in this regard. sports teachers of Colombo, Gampaha schools and sports teachers of Kaluthara schools for the problem of non-support of class teachers for supervision in giving marks in sports activities

More than 50% responded. But the sports teacher of iC school said in the interview, "We get the support of the class teachers, the teachers come down and work sometimes they fight with us, they encourage the children and send them to the field, which means that our class teachers give us enthusiastic support." Not a serious problem. However, interviews in other schools revealed that classroom teachers were least likely to support the implementation of this assessment. Thus, it is revealed that most sports teachers need the support of human resources in implementing this sports-based evaluation system, but do not receive the necessary support for it. Accordingly, it is clear that there is a problem with human resources for all schools and it is revealed that the sports teachers of Kaluthara schools have more of these problems than the sports teachers of other schools.

4.3.3. Financial problems arising in the implementation of the evaluation system based on sports in the school.

Sports Teacher Questionnaire No. 14 to 17 were directed to uncover the financial problems faced by sports teachers in implementing the evaluation system of scoring based on sports for examinations.

TABLE 4.3.3-1 - FINANCIAL PROBLEMS ARISING IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SPORTS-BASED EVALUATION SYSTEM IN SCHOOL

Financial problems	District			Yes / No		Total
	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Yes	No	
Not enough money to buy equipments	5	4	5	14	4	77.7%
There is difficulty in paying to outsourced trainers.	3	4	4	11	7	61.1%
Failure to properly allocate funds from the school to implement this evaluation system	3	2	2	7	11	38.9%
Inadequate sports funding from the government	6	6	6	18	-	100%

In terms of financial problems, the problem that has affected all schools is that the sports aid money received from the government is

not enough to implement the evaluation system based on this sport. It is revealed by the 100% response of all schools. In the

interviews, it was shown that the money allocated by the government is not enough to get sports goods and due to the lack of sports equipment, sports teachers, the abilities of many talented students are wasted.

For the problem of not having money to get the sports equipment needed for sports, 5 sports teachers of Gampaha and Kaluthara schools, and 4 teachers of Kaluthara schools 77%, have responded and in comparison, so this is stronger for all schools in western province schools. It turns out that there is a problem. In the interviews, the sports teacher of one school said, "We don't get enough money to buy sports equipment from the Ministry of Sports. We buy equipment from the school and other forms of aid, but if we wait until we get money from the government, there will be no such thing as sports" because we don't have a swimming pool, but the father of a child in the school. Someone makes those payments voluntarily, so we do swimming for children. If the government does not give those resources, the children will never be able to do swimming." Accordingly, it is clear that lack of money to get sports equipment and those resources is a strong problem and it is revealed that various efforts have been made to improve school sports by solving those problems.

Also, 61% sports teachers of schools have responded to the problem of the difficulty of paying money for sports coaches and sports consultants who are brought in from outside for training, and compared to that, 11 sports teachers of Colombo, Gampaha and Kaluthara schools have responded to it. It reveals that the problem is at a higher level for sports teachers in Colombo and Kaluthara schools than sports teachers in Gampaha schools. Interviews revealed that in many schools, funds are allocated from development societies that the payments are carried out. The sports teachers of schools indicated in the interviews that money is not a strong problem as some sports coaches are involved in running the sports activities of the school voluntarily.

For the problem of not properly allocating the necessary money for the implementation of this sports-based evaluation system in the school, 3 sports teachers of Gampaha and 2 sports teachers of Kaluthara and Colombo schools have given a response of about 28.9%. In comparison to other financial problems, it was revealed in the interviews that this is not a strong problem for Gampaha schools. In the interview, the sports teacher of Gampaha schools said that after the school's development association budgeted and approved by the province, money is allocated to us and a lot of money is allocated from the school for inter-house sports. But for some games such as chess, even if the children bring a small amount of money, they have been charged because the money allocated by the school is not enough, so there is a problem that the allocated amount is not enough. Accordingly, compared to other financial problems, this is not a strong problem for the all schools, the above comments are confirmed.

Accordingly, in the study of the entire sample, the sports subsidy money received from the government was not sufficient for the implementation of this sports-based evaluation system. It is revealed that there is a strong problem for all schools. Overall, both schools have financial problems, but it is revealed that sports teachers in all schools have more problems.

4.3.4. Time management issues in implementing game-based assessment.

Questions 18 - 22 of the Sports Teacher Questionnaire were referred to the questions 18 - 22 of the Sports Teacher Questionnaire for the study of time management issues in the implementation of the evaluation system of giving points for term exams based on games and the following responses were received in the analysis of those questions.

TABLE 4.3.4-1 - TIME MANAGEMENT ISSUES IN IMPLEMENTING GAME-BASED ASSESSMENT

Time management problem	District			Yes / No		Total
	Gampaha	Colombo	Kaluthara	Yes	No	
Not having enough time to monitor and score students as they play	4	5	4	13	5	72.2%
Not having enough time to practice to match the marks awarded	3	4	4	11	7	61.1%
Giving more time to learning in classrooms and less time to sports activities	5	5	5	15	3	83.3%
Reduced student attendance due to implementation after school hours	5	5	6	16	2	88.8%
A small number of sports teachers have to supervise and train a large number of students in a short period of time	3	2	5	10	8	55.5%

In terms of time management in the implementation of this game-based evaluation system, the strongest problem that has arisen for all sports teachers in all schools is the problem of reduced attendance of students during the implementation of this game-based evaluation system after school. It is a 88.8% Percentage. During the interviews, the sports teachers of Gampaha school said, "The amount of staying in the evening is less. Because children go to extra classes in the evening, that is the main reason for the decrease in students, but now we have matches in each event to increase the number of children staying and playing in the evening. When we win a match, Children who are not in the event that day are also trained in the evening

In order to do this, they are trying to get the children to participate in the game by using various tactics, and in Gampaha schools, "only the students who always participate participate, because the other students do not participate, the non-participating students lose a lot of points in giving marks." According to the comments made in the discussions, it is revealed that the problem of low attendance of students in the implementation after the completion of the school is strong and various strategies have been used to reduce the problem.

Also, sports teachers of Colombo schools have given a high response to the problem of giving more time to classroom learning and getting

limited time for sports activities, it is revealed as a high level problem for sports teachers of schools. Sports teachers of Colombo schools have also given responses to that, which reveals that it is the second problem for Kaluthara schools. In the interviews, it was revealed that as well as classroom work, sports are necessary to produce a child with a healthy personality, so more time should be given to sports. That's why today's children have become sick, sports is an opportunity to get rid of the exam mentality, it is necessary to direct the children to this with the support of other teachers" were presented by the sports teachers.

School teachers gave a response of 55.5% for the problems of not having enough time to supervise and give marks when doing certain sports. It is revealed that it is a problem for sports teachers of Colombo, Kaluthara schools more than sports teachers of Gampaha schools. During the interviews, it was revealed that since a large group of students schools practice in the morning, there have been problems regarding time in ensuring their attendance and supervision. Responses of sports teachers of schools revealed that it is a problem for sports teachers

For the problem of not having enough time to practice sports to match the marks given to the students, the sports teachers of schools have responded the percentage is 61.1%. Accordingly, it is revealed that the sports

teachers of schools have the same problem. In the study of the entire sample, it is revealed that the problem of low attendance of the students in the implementation of this game-based assessment system after school is strong, with 88.8% response from all schools. Accordingly, all schools had problems with time management, but it is revealed that sports teachers in Colombo schools have more problems with time management than sports teachers in other schools. Accordingly, under this objective, a whole to the sports teachers of both types of schools This reveals that physical, human resources, financial and time management issues have arisen and this evaluation system is being implemented by facing those problems to award marks based on sports for term examinations

4.4.Problems and difficulties faced by students in participating in the evaluation system

Students were the main target used for data collection under the above objective. A total of 210 students were selected as a sample of 70 students per school in the selected schools, A

questionnaire was given to identify the problems and difficulties that arise. For further in-depth study of those issues, interviews were conducted with two students from among the 70 students selected in each school. The main problems they face were investigated in three areas. There the student presented questions from 11 to 23 of the questionnaire.

01 Students' interest in this game-based assessment.

02 Problems that arise in relation to the game-based evaluation system difficulty

03 Issues arising in connection with awarding of points in the implementation of game-based evaluation system

4.4.1. Problems with interest in this game-based evaluation system

Under this, the student was referred to sub questions 11, 12 of the questionnaire. The responses given there are, Issues arising regarding the interest of students towards game-based scoring system for term exams of students

TABLE 4.4.1-1 - PROBLEMS WITH INTEREST IN THIS GAME-BASED EVALUATION SYSTEM

Problems related to students interests	District						Total sample		
	Gampaha		Colombo		Kaluthara		Quantity		%
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Compulsory participation in sports that are disliked.	19	51	10	60	25	45	54	156	25.7%
Sports that the student likes to engage in are not included in this evaluation system	39	31	45	25	58	12	142	68	67.6%

In the study of the problems that arise in relation to the students' interest in the evaluation system of giving points for term exams based on sports, 67.6% students responded that the main problem is that the sports activities that you want to engage in are not included in this evaluation system. is indicated. In schools, activities such as cricket and chess have not been used in this evaluation system to give marks and only athletics and other sports have been used. There is a willingness to engage with and under-skilled groups, but this evaluation system has not been used and scored. It was also revealed in the interviews that they had to play games unwillingly due to non-like.

Accordingly, the entire sample in the study is a 25.7% response to the problem of having to participate in sports that you dislike in this sports-based evaluation system, and a higher response of 67/6% is that the activities that you like to engage in are not included in this evaluation system. It is revealed that this problem has been the main problem for the students of schools. Accordingly, it is revealed that the students of western province schools have problems related to interest and those problems are more common among the students of western province schools.

4.4.2 Difficulties encountered by students in participating in this game-based assessment program

Questions 13 to 19 of the student questionnaire were addressed to study the difficulties faced

by students in participating in this game-based assessment program.

TABLE 4.4.2-1 - DIFFICULTIES FACED BY STUDENTS IN PARTICIPATING IN THIS GAME-BASED ASSESSMENT PROGRAM

Problems faced by students while participating in evaluation	District						Total sample		
	Gampaha		Colombo		Kaluthara		Quantity		%
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Non-availability of transportation to participate in this evaluation process	56	14	53	17	52	18	161	49	76.7%
The student has to spend evening time for this evaluation method	65	5	64	6	68	2	197	13	93.8%
This evaluation method is a hindrance to the student's participation in extra classes	62	8	61	9	65	5	188	22	89.5%
Disruption to classroom subject learning while participating in this assessment system	35	35	35	35	38	32	108	102	51.4%
Due to this evaluation system, the student is overtired and misses the lessons	58	12	50	20	55	15	163	47	77.6%
Failure to balance these assessment activities and subject teaching activities for the student	61	9	58	12	55	15	174	36	82.9%
Being accused of skipping school cleaning due to these assessment methods	42	28	60	10	66	4	168	42	80%

In the study of the difficulties faced by students in participating in this game-based assessment program, 2 main difficulties for students in schools can be identified: the problem of using their evening time for this assessment system and the problem that this game-based assessment system hinders you from participating in their extra classes. The problems of being, are the main problems so identified. It is revealed that 93.8% of the students of western province schools have given a high response to those problems. Students in Kaluthara schools also indicated that using their evening time for this assessment method was a major problem with a high response of 68. In the interviews in school children, it was revealed that "if you

study in the class from morning and play sports in the morning, you can play outside fresh, and in Gampaha schools, there are classes where there is no way for students to play games in the afternoon." Even if you don't go to the extra classes, you have to attend the evening practices in the school. , because the school practices and extra classes are held in the evening, there is a problem for the students to participate in the games in the evening, and there is a reluctance of the parents to participate in the games without attending the classes. It also appears that the attitude of parents towards sports needs to be developed. According responses reveal that the problem of lack of transportation facilities is

greater than other difficulties for students western province schools.

According to responses 82% responded as they unable to balance their academic activities because of this game based evaluation system. Gampaha students face this problem more than other schools.

It is revealed that students of Gampaha school have that problem at a higher level than students of other schools. In the interviews, it was revealed that it is not a problem for the students whose houses are near the school, but many students come to school early in the morning, engage in sports training until 5 in the evening, and there is no transport facility to go home, and parents also have to come to the school to pick up the students. And it is revealed that they face many difficulties.

80% of the students of schools gave the same response to the problem of keeping sports-based evaluation activities and subject teaching activities seriously and being accused of skipping the cleaning activities of the school due to the sports-based evaluation system. The students of Gampaha schools have also responded less than Colombo and Kaluthara schools for the same problems. In the interviews, "Since the school sports practice starts at 6:00 in the morning, when all the children who are playing sports, go to the games, Miss Klashara always scolds her for not playing sports. Even though she teaches in the first period, she says that she finishes with

the sports. According to the interviews, It was revealed that since the school sports practice starts from 6.00 in the morning, almost all the people who have to clean that day are engaged in sports practice, so the teachers in charge are accused of not doing the morning cleaning properly and also using the time available to study in the classroom for cleaning. Because of this, it is revealed that there is another problem.

In the study of the whole sample, it is revealed that the students face many difficulties in participating in this game-based evaluation program and the problem of using their evening time for this evaluation system is the main problem for both types of schools, Accordingly, it is revealed that students of western province schools have problems and difficulties in participating in this evaluation system.

4.4.3 Difficulties arising in awarding marks to students participating in this game-based assessment programme.

Questions 20-22 were addressed to study the issues arising in scoring for the game-based evaluation system. Accordingly, I discovered the problematic and non-problematic situations here.

TABLE 4.4.3-1 - ISSUES ARISING IN AWARDING POINTS IN IMPLEMENTATION OF GAME-BASED EVALUATION SYSTEM

Problems faced by students while participating in this evaluation system	District						Total sample		
	Gampaha		Colombo		Kaluthara		Quantity		%
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Strongly influencing the student to change in the class because of the marks given by this evaluation system	23	47	19	51	26	44	68	142	32.4%
In this evaluation system, not recording the student's attendance correctly and adding marks to the progress report book	6	64	12	58	18	52	36	174	17.1%
Students who are good at sports benefit from this assessment system	2	68	7	63	5	65	14	193	6.6%

In the study of the difficulties in giving marks to students in participating in this game-based evaluation program, the main problem for western province schools is that the marks given through this evaluation system have a strong impact on the difference in the class. Students have given a response of 32.4% for that problem. Interviews revealed that for most students, the extra points they get from sports are not a problem as it helps them to get higher grades in the class. It is revealed that this is a problem for some students by indicating that students who do not participate in sports regularly will have to go down to the lower grades in the paper due to the decrease in marks.

Also, responded 17.1% of students for the problems of not recording your attendance correctly and reporting the relevant scores in the sports-based evaluation system. That turns out to be a problem. Interviews revealed that attendance in some schools is recorded through a signature register and is not a major problem as it is verified by sports teachers once a month. In the interviews, the students said that "some days when the bell rings, Ms. forgets that she has come in our sports book, we remind her and mark it as Ms. is revealed.

6.6% of the students gave a response to the problem that students who are good at sports have an advantage through this sports-based evaluation system, The students of the school said in the interviews that because the physical test gives 100 points, the children who are good at sports can get more marks than the children who can't do sports." It is revealed that this is a strong problem for the students of the school as they have to face a practical test giving 100 points under the evaluation system of giving points based on sports to the students and where the students who are good at sports get more points. But in other schools, as marks are given based on participation, it is revealed from the interviews that it is not a strong problem for students who are good at sports as well as incompetent. In the study of the entire sample, is there a strong effect on the difference in the class because of the marks given through this evaluation method? A response for the problem reveals that it is a strong problem for all types of schools. Thus, the students It is revealed that there are problems with scoring while participating in the sports-based assessment system, and

students from sports schools have more of those problems.

Thus, it is revealed that there are many problems and difficulties faced by the students while participating in the evaluation system of giving points based on the game for term exams and it is revealed that the students of sports schools face those problems.

5 Conclusion and Future Scope

5.1 Conclusions

- 1) In giving points for the sports-based evaluation system, in all the 3 sports schools, a certain sport has been selected and practiced and the activities organized by the schools according to seasons, it seems that schools have been used to give points for this evaluation system. .
- 2) To select any game for this evaluation system and provide points Field games, like cricket, netball and football are used and for indoor games, Less chance is given.
- 3) Revealed that these are sports schools but there are not enough physical resources for schools. The conclusion is between sports school that there is an inequality in the distribution of resources.
- 4) It is concluded that schools Gampaha and Colombo practice longer than other schools in addition to 5 days a week even on holidays.
- 5) Every school is trained for 3-4 hours in giving lice for this evaluation system in schools.

In the implementation of this indication system, every school conducts sports training before and after the start of school, and physical fitness program during school hours. Therefore, it is concluded that teaching time is not used for this evaluation system.

- 6) sports school, students have been given the opportunity to score points through various activities. 40, 20, 20, 20 points are divided into small parts for a total of 100 points. is given to the students. Accordingly, it can be concluded that this system is implemented by distributing marks more formally in the sports school than the other three schools. The students of the sports school have to take a practical test and face it and get these 100 marks. Therefore, the students who are incompetent in sports It is concluded that it is a somewhat disadvantageous situation, but it can be

concluded that every gifted and incompetent student will not be treated unfairly as the evaluation of other schools is done on the basis of participation and active contribution. It is concluded that sports teachers and sports coaches contribute more to the supervision of these evaluation activities. It is revealed that a total of 100 marks have been given to students based on sports activities as recommended by the Ministry for this evaluation system.

- 7) It is revealed that by maintaining a book that records the sports activities in all the 3 schools, attendance marks related to this indication are made and by giving the books to the teacher in charge, the sports teachers add them to the progress report book and give marks for the students' term exams. Accordingly, it can be concluded that the order of giving marks is done in a formal manner.
- 8) It can be concluded that both students and teachers have a positive attitude regarding the counter-cognitive statements of the students and teachers about the game-based assessment system.
- 9) Regarding the negative statements about the game-based evaluation system, it is concluded that most of the teachers have a negative attitude towards the game-based evaluation system and the students have a good attitude for the other statements except the 9th statement. Accordingly, it is concluded that there are both good and bad attitudes in teachers and students regarding this game-based evaluation system.
- 10) The conclusion that the problems related to the physical resources required for sports and lack of equipment and buildings for sports are the main problems for both schools in Gampaha and Kaluthara. can do It is also revealed that sports teachers in both schools have more problems related to physical resources than sports teachers in colombo
- 11) Absence of sports coaches and sports instructors in required quantity Gampaha and Kaluthara as the main human resource related problem in both schools can be concluded. And Gampaha and Kaluthara schools have more human resource problem is revealed.
- 12) The strongest financial problem for all schools is revealed as the problem that the

sports aid money received from the government is not enough to implement this evaluation system. It is also revealed that sports teachers in Kaluthara schools have more financial problems than sports teachers in Gampaha and colombo schools.

- 13) Among the problems that arise in terms of time management for sports teachers, the problem of minimum attendance of students during the implementation of the sports-based evaluation system after school can be indicated as the strongest problem for all schools. It is also revealed that sports teachers in Gampaha and Colombo schools have more problems with time management than sports teachers in Kaluthara schools.
- 14) Among the problems that arise for students regarding the interest of students in participating in the sports-based evaluation system, the problem that the activities that students like to engage in are not included in this evaluation system can be concluded as the strongest problem for students in all schools.
- 15) The problem of using students in the evening for this assessment method is revealed as the strongest problem for the students of all schools in participating in this assessment. In addition, this game-based assessment system is a hindrance to attending extra classes.
- 16) It can be concluded that the problem of difference in the class in terms of giving marks in the implementation of the sports-based evaluation system is the strongest problem for the students of sports schools. According to all these conclusions, it can be seen that the sports teachers implement the sports-based evaluation system. and the students also participate in this evaluation system and get marks and develop their sports skills. But they have many difficulties and problems and There is a positive relationship between teachers' attitudes and students' attitudes towards this assessment method.

5.2 Future scope

5.2.1 Sports teachers' suggestions

Following are the suggestions made by the students and sports teachers to develop the evaluation system for giving marks for term exams based on the sports in the schools

according to the data obtained through the objectives 1,2,3,4 above.

- 1) To educate students about the ability of students who are weak in subjects to advance in the class by getting more marks through this game-based assessment system.
- 2) Increasing the total number of points awarded for the game-based assessment system will increase the student's ability to engage in the sports.
- 3) Increasing the amount of activities used in this assessment system to score students
- 4) In many schools, points are not given to the less talented students and the activities organized by the school, and those activities are also included in this evaluation system to develop the sports skills of the students by giving them points.
- 5) Regular daily maintenance of the book that records the sports activities of the students.
- 6) To further inform students, parents and other teachers about the marks that students can get in term exams by participating in competitions such as divisions, district zones, all Sri Lanka.
- 7) Extension of time for students to practice sports
- 8) To make children and students understand the importance of sports.
- 9) Informing parents and other teachers of the school about this game. Opinion-based evaluation method
- 10) To give knowledge to the students about how to develop personality through sports
- 11) Preparing cleaning schedules together with classroom teachers and sports teachers so that students can engage in cleaning activities on non-training days.
- 12) Directing students to complete classroom cleaning in the evening before the day of sports practice so that they can engage in morning sports practice activities without interruption
- 13) Making the students participate in the training in the morning as much as possible so that there is no disruption to the extra class etc.
- 14) Parents should be informed and explain the importance of sports in the evening Enlisting their support to provide security for training.
- 15) Informing the sports teachers about the possible cases of injury due to excessive training load by providing over limit practice in the relevant time frame.
- 16) Educating the sports teachers to bring out the talents by giving time to the child naturally without over-exerting the students. As well as

for parents about the benefits and timeliness of sports Informing the school teachers also To make parents and students understand the value of sports and games Explaining the opportunities that can lead them to higher education.

17) Making the best use of the available sports equipment to produce healthy and sports-oriented children.

18) To introduce opportunities for higher education by teaching health and physical education along with sports.

19) To make students understand the importance of physical health.

20) Presenting requests together as a sports organization at the school level due to insufficient funds allocated for sports.

21) Providing residential training to students with transportation difficulties

22) Evaluating Student Performance.

23) Establishment of a sports fund in school.

24) Sports teachers refer them to training sessions to update their knowledge doing

25) Providing a sports coach to each school Providing sports coaches specific to each sport

26) Students with talent in sports are identified and presented for national competitions training them,

27) I explain that through playing games, students' social skills develop.

28) Sports and physical fitness are essential for a healthy mind and healthy saliva Explanation

29) Sports training activities are happy contributors in such a way that students are not unhappy Doing it without difficulty as a matter of course

30) Providing the required amount of sports training teachers to the schools

31) Conduct training sessions to professional level for non-sports teachers when they volunteer for sports training.

32) This game-based assessment system supervises and evaluates principals Conducting under

33) Reduce negative attitudes of students towards sports and more for sports Using tactics to retain a group of students

5.2.2 Student Proposals

- 1) Sports activity that students are most interested in this assessment method It can be used to motivate students to engage with sports.

- 2) days count Conducting various sports trainings.
- 3) To maintain the continuity of training activities, since it is difficult to carry out sports activities and training in the morning hours, as much as possible, training in the morning hours.
- 4) Not using school time for training activities Applying alternative measures through school to avoid transportation difficulties
- 5) Inform the sports teachers to record the attendance of the students as scheduled and arrange for the relevant scores to be given to the teachers in charge of the classes at the appointed time so that the teachers in charge of the classes can avoid the inconvenience caused in the separation and preparation of the class.
- 6) Employing sports specific teachers
- 7) Providing adequate physical facilities for training activities

5.2.3 Future Research Suggestions

- To study the reasons why the game-based scoring system for term exams is not being formally implemented in the entire school system.
- A study on how game-based scoring system affects student's personality performance for term examinations.
- Inquiring the attitude of teachers, students and parents about the game-based scoring system for 3-term examinations

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